

T
FACTOR |

PARTICIPATORY FUTURES

Regenerating cities
with
temporary uses

ADVANCED CASES PORTFOLIO

Portfolio summary

This document addresses the topic of **temporary or meanwhile uses in urban regeneration** and results from research work developed within T-Factor, a **Horizon 2020** project that seeks to boost temporary uses as a driving force for more inclusive, thriving and resilient urban regeneration.

The document is conceived as a Portfolio - i.e. a compendium of stories, highlights and learnings emerging from the adoption or emergence of temporary uses within eight urban redevelopments across Europe and beyond, namely **Manifattura Tabacchi** in Florence, **King's Cross** in London, **Friche Belle de Mai** in Marseille, **22@** in Barcelona, **ECT and New Centre** in Lodz, **Dortmunder U and Union Quarter** in Dortmund, **Industry City** in New York and **Red Town** in Shanghai. In T-Factor, these are the so-called **Advanced Cases**: regeneration initiatives that are nearly completed or at advanced stages, and where temporary uses are a key feature of the redevelopment pathway. Their diversity - in terms of geographical areas and cultures, socio-economic contexts, heritage, types of regeneration projects - may offer a multitude of insights around a field of practice and policymaking which is still emergent across Europe, thus contributing to knowledge creation and learning.

The highlights and stories captured in this Portfolio are mostly practical; by covering a wide range of aspects that are at play when dealing with temporary uses in urban regeneration, we attempt to provide developers, public authorities, intermediaries and practitioners with useful indications and ideas to unlock their potential towards more sustainable, inclusive and higher quality regeneration. More than that, we intend for this Portfolio to contribute to a wide reflection and conversation around the multiple values and possible risks that temporary uses may bring about in making our cities a better place for all.

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T-Factor

PARTICIPATORY FUTURES REGENERATING CITIES WITH TEMPORARY USES

T-Factor is a **Horizon 2020 Innovation Action** dedicated to the topic of **temporary or meanwhile uses in urban regeneration**. In the project, we argue that the time factor in urban regeneration can become a strategic asset when it is used as a means of collective place prototyping in light of stable uses and functions. It's a win-win situation for all stakeholders - governments, developers, academia, business, grassroots communities and citizens.

Our mission is to build a full portfolio of tested innovations embracing design, organisation, management, governance, funding and regulatory aspects of temporary spaces, so as to contribute to unlocking their transformative potential toward inclusive, sustainable and thriving cities.

[Discover more](#)

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About the Portfolio

This portfolio contains **highlights and stories of temporary uses** in the context of urban regeneration initiatives across Europe and beyond.

Some of these initiatives - the redevelopment of **King's Cross** in London, **22@** in Barcelona, **Friche Belle de Mai** in Marseille, **Red Town** in Shanghai, **EC1 and New Centre** in Lodz - have long roots, evolving over decades alongside the major breakthroughs of our recent history, including the 2008 financial crisis, the booming of the digital economy and the rise of the so-called creative class. Others - **Dortmunder U and Union Quarter** in Dortmund, **Industry City** in New York and **Manifattura Tabacchi** in Florence - are more recent, positioning themselves in the new wave of urban redevelopments that has started to characterise cities since the mid 2000s. In **T-Factor** these initiatives are the so-called **advanced cases** (henceforth, also referred to as ACs) that form our primary source of knowledge and learning on **temporary uses** in urban regeneration, which will be leveraged and further expanded in the context of six early-stage regeneration initiatives across Europe¹.

Indeed, for all of these initiatives, it is hard to identify

one moment in time when their regeneration story actually began, and it is much more difficult to say whether regeneration dynamics are fully completed or if they are ongoing. As Prof. Peter Bishop said in a recent T-Factor's webinar², "*cities exist in open-ended transformations and evolutions, and good urban regeneration essentially enables what happens next*". Certainly, regardless of their individual story, all of these initiatives have their roots in the same history - one marked by urban production and consumption being globalised, and our urban assets - public and private, material and immaterial - increasingly becoming the fundamental means of value extraction to the advantage of the few.

The positive role that **temporary uses** can play in reversing abandonment and blank spaces in cities is relatively well understood. Recent European projects such as Refill³ and Living Streets⁴ are some examples - among many others - documenting a rich variety of temporary initiatives popping up here and there in our cities. International media such as The Guardian⁵, local governments such as the Greater London Authority and global consultancies such as ARUP⁶ have also put their spotlight on temporary uses, describing them as a viable alternative to traditional placemaking and the opportunity to respond to existing and emerging needs, including to the aftermath of the Covid 19 pandemic.

In this Portfolio, we explore temporary uses with the lens of urban regeneration processes and system dynamics. More specifically, we focus on the time period in between the masterplan or pre-masterplan approval on the one hand, and the actual delivery of the regenerated areas on the other hand. In this specific period, spaces assume a particular temporary character, essentially becoming **spaces in waiting** - i.e. spaces whose destiny is somehow defined at the outset and whose temporary presence and experience is constrained to a predetermined schedule of execution.

We argue that with an increase in the scale of urban regenerations and growing risks of failure vis-à-vis rapid and disruptive change, temporary uses can become a lever for more flexible and resilient regeneration processes. More than that, they can ignite the shift from spaces *in waiting* to spaces that anticipate preferred futures, **transforming masterplans' trajectories toward higher ambitions of quality of life and prosperity for all.**

None of the ACs may have fully reached this frontier so far. Rather, each of them may contain some of the seeds and learnings needed for a holistic and systemic approach to temporary uses, and therefore for a fully transformative approach to the way we equip our cities for the future. By shining the spotlight on such seeds and learning, we intend for this Portfolio to contribute to inspiring and triggering a new wave of urban developments, driven by people, for people and the planet.

² Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n-miq6hgxcQ&t=227s>

³ <https://urbact.eu/Refill>

⁴ <http://www.livingstreets.energy-cities.eu/the-challenge.html>

⁵ The rise of the 'meanwhile space': how empty properties are finding second lives, The Guardian, 28-11-2018, available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/cities/2018/nov/28/the-rise-of-the-meanwhile-space-how-empty-properties-are-finding-second-lives>

⁶ https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/meanwhile_use_for_london_final.pdf

¹ More in detail, the six early-stage regeneration sites (T-Factor's Pilots) are: Trafaria in Lisbon, MIND Milan, Amsterdam Science Park, Zorrotzaurre in Bilbao, Aleksotas in Kaunas and Euston in London. See: www.t-factor.eu

Portfolio Methodology

The Portfolio is the result of research work developed between June 2020 and March 2021 and marks the first step of the **T-Factor** project towards a better understanding of the role of temporary uses as catalysts for impactful urban regeneration. The research analysed temporary use in the context of eight advanced regeneration initiatives across European cities and beyond⁷, in order to build a rich set of findings and learnings meant to inspire ongoing and future redevelopments.

The work - which has involved an extensive team of researchers and practitioners from various T-Factor's partners⁸, all coordinated by the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya - began with data collection and review of relevant documentation about the regeneration initiatives, including official master-planning documentation, media articles, policy and research documents, evaluation and impact assessment reports, where available.

In a second stage, we undertook a round of interviews with key regeneration stakeholders, in order to gain a better understanding of how the regeneration began, the challenges intended to be addressed at the outset, the vision and positioning, the approach to meanwhile uses, among other strategic aspects. The voices heard at this stage were mainly those of developers,

local authorities and meanwhile 'orchestrators' or intermediaries (i.e. people who have designed and managed meanwhile activation strategies). Subsequently, a small number of meanwhile projects⁹ were identified for each AC, attempting to select not only those considered 'successful' in terms of site reactivation, public engagement, collaborative placemaking and creation of new opportunities; we also selected controversial cases that have generated conflict, perceived dynamics of exclusion and disempowerment of local communities. In this respect, the direct knowledge of the regeneration initiatives by the local research teams has been key to mitigating the risk of harvesting stories biased by the point of view of developers or a few stakeholders only. Meanwhile interventions were analysed by means of relevant documentation and media articles review, as well as via interviews with initiators, in some cases also with direct beneficiaries. Where available, we also considered insights from surveys developed by municipalities and local authorities to assess citizens' feelings and perceptions around the regeneration initiatives, in the attempt to broaden the points of view mapped out.

Intermediate checkpoints gathering all researchers together also helped share ongoing learning and discovery, and to map out emerging highlights, both common and case specific. The last step of the work consisted of an in-depth analysis of all individual reports elaborated by the local research teams, with a mapping and clustering of insights and findings finally captured in this portfolio.

The methodology described above was applied to the six European ACs; for the non-European ones - Industry City in New York and Red Town in Shanghai - the work was limited in depth and scope, due to Covid 19 restrictions and the difficulty to reach out to the key regeneration stakeholders.

It is worth highlighting that the findings and learnings captured in the Portfolio largely come from the perspective of a few types of actors, mainly developers, local authorities, intermediaries and practitioners of temporary uses. Our intent with this work has been to explore temporary uses mainly from the perspective of 'who' drives urban redevelopments, in order to better understand if and to what extent these emerging practices come with new mindsets, cultures and approaches to urban regeneration. Further investigation is certainly needed to contrast and further expand the content of this Portfolio with the fundamental point of view of citizens.

⁷ The initiatives, or T-Factor's Advanced Cases are: Manifattura Tabacchi in Florence, King's Cross in London, Friche Belle de Mai in Marseille, 22@ in Barcelona, ECI and New Centre in Lodz, Dortmund U and Union Quarter in Dortmund, Industry City in New York and Red Town in Shanghai.

⁸ In addition to the coordinator Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, the T-Factor partners involved in the research are: LAMA Agency, TU Dortmund University, Friche La Belle de Mai, University of the Arts London Central Saint Martins, City of Lodz, University of Łódź, Tongji University, ANCI Toscana, iPropeller, KPMG.

⁹ On average, we analysed three meanwhile projects for each regeneration initiative. However, in some cases the number was slightly higher especially where meanwhile practices have been mobilised at scale and with important financial investment. It is also worth highlighting that for each AC, the landscape of meanwhile projects actually developed is richer than what is captured in this Portfolio, which cannot therefore be considered representative.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to all the people who contributed to this Portfolio, making available and openly sharing their own experience, knowledge and points of view. Indeed, these people are just a small part of the broader ecosystem of actors and stakeholders at stake in each regeneration site; their insights and points of view do not embrace the much richer spectrum of voices and stories that certainly exist across the ACs, and that we could not hear from given the limited time frame and relatively narrow scope of this work.

Yet, their contributions have been key to shedding light on the role that meanwhile uses can play in urban regeneration, and the added value they can bring about to make our cities for the better.

Moreover, their direct experience - often as practitioners in the field - has allowed us to lay the foundations for discovery and learning not only in the context of this work, but rather for the whole T-Factor project which will keep running in the coming years. We are particularly grateful to Francesca Valsecchi and Kendall Tichner who, from two different continents and related time zones during Covid 19 restrictions, have dedicated energy to sharing precious information and insights about the two non-European regeneration initiatives addressed in this document.

We hope in this Portfolio none of the voices heard have been neglected, and none of the findings misinterpreted. The authors remain fully responsible for the content of this document.

Portfolio glossary

/Temporary use

Temporary use is a practice in urbanism aiming to revitalise empty spaces in urban areas, especially abandoned and decaying buildings. Many spaces are left empty by owners because they currently do not have plans for the space, no capital for its renovation or further building, or cannot sell or rent the space at the price they want. Instead of waiting with an empty space, which can often mean being additionally taxed by the municipality, they can offer a temporary use. This allows various community members to obtain the space for their social, cultural, or other needs, often under more favourable terms. The property owner often has less requirements than in the case of a normal lease: they do not have to maintain the space and can cancel the use at a much shorter notice. On the other hand, temporary users can use the space at no or symbolical cost, and often maintain the spaces themselves. (source: [Wikipedia](#))

/Meanwhile use

A “meanwhile use” describes a situation where a site is utilised for a duration of time before it is turned into a more permanent end state, taking advantage of a short window of opportunity.

Meanwhile interventions are tactical and slot into wider strategies of planned change. They can help in shaping positive urban transformation. We evidence the transitional nature of meanwhile uses within urban development, where its primary purpose is to deliver benefits to the community through predominantly social outcomes as well as economic and environmental. It is not exclusive of its users but inclusive of social need; it delivers social value, informs longer-term development and drives a new vision of city making (ARUP, 2020). Not all temporary uses are meanwhile: meanwhile uses take advantage of a window of opportunity on a site, before and after another use. And not all meanwhile uses are short term. Some meanwhile uses are offered long leases, for instance in regeneration projects spanning decades. (Source: [Centre for London](#), 2018).

/Waiting time and spaces *in waiting*

Waiting time: the specific time period in urban regeneration that stands between the approval of the masterplan or pre-masterplan on the one hand, and the delivery of the regenerated areas on the other hand.

Spaces *in waiting*: those spaces that, in the context of urban regeneration processes, are temporary for a predefined period of time, and where permanent functions and uses are somehow already defined in masterplans and planning documents. In this period, the temporary character of spaces is more or less determined at the outset, and it deals with a context where investors are there, functions and positionings are outlined, and specific planning, construction and consultation procedures are at play.

/Placemaking

As both an overarching idea and a hands-on approach for improving a neighbourhood, city, or region, placemaking inspires people to collectively reimagine and reinvent public spaces as the heart of every community. Strengthening the connection between people and the places they share, placemaking refers to a collaborative process by which we can shape our public realm in order to maximize shared value. More than just promoting better urban design, placemaking facilitates creative patterns of use, paying particular attention to the physical, cultural, and social identities that define a place and support its ongoing evolution (Source: [Project for Public Spaces](#)).

/Meanwhile Orchestrators and intermediaries

Organisations or professionals that explicitly operate in the design and management of meanwhile activation strategies. Intermediaries also include organisations or teams of professionals with expertise in matchmaking between demand and offer of vacant spaces, as well as in the support to the start-up of temporary uses.

/Hardware and Software in Urban Regeneration

The ‘hardware’ side of urban regeneration is usually associated with “infrastructure, architecture and housing”, while the ‘software’ with the ‘main operating rules that help a city to be functional and

Portfolio glossary

sustainable'. Therefore, while the hardware relates to the physical infrastructure being redeveloped, the software is the set of organizational, economic and social principles inspiring a good quality of life and of human relations in cities. (Mohelig, 2017).

/Public value

Public value describes the value that an organization contributes to society. The term was originally coined by Harvard professor Mark H. Moore who saw it as the equivalent of shareholder value in public management. Public value is supposed to provide managers with a notion of how entrepreneurial activity can contribute to the common good. Nowadays, public value is no longer limited to the public sector, but is used by all types of organization, including non-governmental organizations and private sector firms. (Source: [Wikipedia](#)).

/Infrastructuring

The intentional action of providing the means for experimentation, discovery and learning within a steering and coordination framework that supports both present and future collaborations (Thorpe and Manzini, 2018).

'The work of creating socio-technical resources that intentionally enable adoption and appropriation beyond the initial scope of the design, a process that might include participants not present during the initial design' (Le Dantec and Di Salvo, 2013).

/Co-benefits

A co-benefits approach is a win-win strategy aimed at capturing both development and climate benefits in a single policy or measure. The term "co-benefits" appeared in the academic literature in the 1990s and generated wider interest around the time of the Third Assessment Report (AR3) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published in 2001. The IPCC AR3 distinguished co-benefits or the intended positive side effects of a policy from ancillary benefits or unintended positive side effects. As BOX1 shows, "side benefits", "secondary benefits", "collateral benefits", and "associated benefits" have also been used to connote similar ideas - the term may be used here for general purposes beyond climate change policies. (Source: [Asian Co-benefits Partnership](#)).

TERMINOLOGY NOTE

At European level, the topic of temporary uses in urban regeneration is a field of action, policy making and research that still lacks consolidated concepts, terminology and unambiguous understanding. Historically, the terms used to describe the reuse and reactivation of vacant, leftover and unused spaces in cities have been many, such as 'temporary use', 'interim use', 'pop up use', 'transient use' and the more recent term 'meanwhile use'.

Moreover, language and geography also matter, with place-based terms such as 'tiers lieux', 'broedplaats', 'spazi occasionali' that might get lost in translation, therefore adding to ambiguity and misinterpretation. In this Portfolio we mainly use terms such as 'temporary use', 'temporary spaces', 'meanwhile use', 'meanwhile spaces' interchangeably to generally refer to activities that take place in blank, vacant and unused spaces in cities.

However, this Portfolio explores a specific type of temporary spaces: those spaces that, in the context of urban regeneration processes, are temporary for a predefined period of time, and where permanent uses are somehow already defined in masterplans and planning documents. In the Portfolio, we often use terms such as 'spaces in waiting', 'waiting spaces' and 'waiting time' to refer to this specific type of spaces.

Key discoveries

Urban regeneration is essentially an *infrastructuring* process aimed at weaving people, places and functions around paradigms of urban living that replace or radically transform the pre-existing ones.

In a context of rising uncertainty and shared vulnerabilities, the way we choose to develop communities determines whether and to what extent urban regeneration can successfully stand the time test – acknowledging and enabling the fundamental nature of permanent transformation of our urban fabrics.

As this Portfolio will show, temporary uses in urban regeneration can bring about multiple forms of value across strategic, operational and relational aspects.

KEY DISCOVERIES

/DISCOVERY 3

The relational value of temporary uses

Temporary uses can **increase the chances of long term thriving urban regeneration**, by:

- > Creating wide agency and legitimacy to transform urban regeneration into collective discovery for better futures
- > Establishing relational capital that contributes to social trust and cohesion
- > Unleash shared urban assets

/DISCOVERY 2

The operational value of temporary uses

Temporary uses can **increase the effectiveness of the regeneration process**, by:

- > Reactivating sites quickly and productively throughout regeneration processes
- > Responding to multiple needs and creating opportunities for different actors to engage with and benefit from opportunities arising from redevelopments
- > Unlocking pooling of resources around shared objectives
- > Setting the terrain for policy and regulatory innovation zones

/DISCOVERY 1

The strategic value of temporary uses

Temporary uses can **enhance the value of the regeneration process**, by:

- > Accommodating experimental and learning by doing placemaking which can unlock more flexible regeneration processes
- > Supporting the uptake of shared responsibilities that create better capacity to address and mitigate shared challenges and risks
- > Facilitating the alignment of agendas and roadmaps across public and private players

ADVANCED CASES

MANIFATTURA TABACCHI

City: Florence
Country: Italy
Characteristics: Industrial heritage related to tobacco industry
Size: 6 hectares
Location: near city centre
Investment: € 300 M approx.
Timeline: 2017 - 2026

DORTMUNDER U and UNION QUARTER

City: Dortmund
Country: Germany
Characteristics: Industrial heritage related to brewery
Size: 155 hectares
Location: near city centre
Investment: € 18,2 M Rheinische Strasse; € 45,79 M Dortmunder U.
Timeline: 2008 - 2018

KING'S CROSS

City: London
Country: UK
Characteristics: Large brownfield area
Size: 27,1 hectares
Location: central
Investment: € 3,45 Bn approx. (£ 3 Bn GBP)
Timeline: 2007 - 2022

FRICHE BELLE DE MAI

City: Marseille
Country: France
Characteristics: Industrial heritage related to tobacco industry
Size: 10 hectares
Location: periphery
Investment: € 45 M approx.
Timeline: 1991 - 2035

22@

City: Barcelona
Country: Spain
Characteristics: Former industrial area; formal recognition of previous informal settlements
Size: 198,26 hectares
Location: semi-periphery
Investment: €180 M approx.
Timeline: 2000 - ongoing (new plan under approval)

EC1 and New Centre Lodz

City: Łódź
Country: Poland
Characteristics: Former industrial area
Size: 100 hectares
Location: central
Investment: € 63 M approx., including € 20 M from the ERDF (only for EC1 and NCL)
Timeline: 2007 - 2022

RED TOWN

City: Shanghai
Country: China
Characteristics: Industrial heritage
Size: 1,8 hectares
Location: central
Investment: Private and public funding
Timeline: 2005 - 2017

INDUSTRY CITY

City: New York
Country: United States of America
Characteristics: Former intermodal manufacturing district; seaport
Size: 14,1 hectares
Location: neighbourhood Brooklyn
Investment: € 2,47 Bn approx. (\$ 1 Bn USD)
Timeline: 2013 - 2025

MANIFATTURA TABACCHI

The new Manifattura Tabacchi is reborn in the former cigar factory closed in March 2001, after more than seventy years of production in which more than 1400 employees worked.

In 2016, the ambitious redevelopment project of the former industrial plant was launched, consisting of 13 buildings in rationalist style, plus 3 new buildings arranged over more than 110,000 square metres of surface area to create a variety of squares, streets and passageways.

With a total investment of €250 million, the promoter of the redevelopment is a joint venture set up in 2016 by the real estate company of the Cassa Depositi e Prestiti Group and Aermont, in its first project in Italy. MTDM Manifattura Tabacchi Development Management Srl is the project management company.

The objective is to complete the work by 2026 and return a new district to the city, animated by the creative energy of fashion, craftsmanship, art and design, a contemporary centre open to all and connected to the world. Manifattura Tabacchi is already hosting permanent and temporary activities capable of activating an organic and sustainable process of growth and offering new reasons to visit Florence.

<https://www.manifatturatabacchi.com/en/>

Photo credits: Niccolò Vonci

FLORENCE
Italy

DORTMUNDER U and UNION QUARTER

For 67 years, the U-Tower or Dortmunder U has been a production facility for beer and therefore embodies an important chapter in the economic history of the city of Dortmund. The history of Dortmund's brewing industry in general and of the "Dortmunder Union" brewery in particular - one of Germany's largest breweries during the 20th century - has always been closely connected to the history of the city. After the brewery closed its doors in 1994, the U-Tower was the only building that was not demolished, thanks to its landmark status. The U-Tower was redeveloped as a flagship project for the "Ruhr 2010 – Cultural Capital of Europe" and it is today one of Dortmund's central places. Dortmunder U embodies an innovative practice at the intersection of art, research, creativity, culture, education and economy. It is a public place for research and study as well as for the experience and the discourse on arts, media and today's culture for citizens of all ages. The operation of the "U" is based on cooperation between different actors, including Ostwall Museum, the Hartware MedienKunstVerein, the Centre for Cultural Education of the City of Dortmund, Dortmund University of Applied Sciences and Arts, TU Dortmund University, the European centre for creative economy and the U Cinema association. The top of the tower is well known for the video installation Flying Pictures by Adolf Winkelmann. The renovation of Dortmunder U and the Ruhr region's appointment as European Capital of Culture is also linked to the urban regeneration of several quarters throughout Dortmund, among them Rheinische Straße, rebranded as Union Quarter.

<https://www.dortmunder-u.de/en>

Photo credits: Hannes Woidich

DORTMUND Germany

KING'S CROSS

King's Cross is one of London's largest and most high-profile developments, covering a large area of land historically in use as railway infrastructure: predominately a network of rail tracks and industrial warehouses surrounded by social housing. After the decline of the railway industry in 1945, the area went from being a busy industrial district to an under-used site where many of the buildings were left vacant but despite this there occurred a variety of uses in the area such as nightclubs, artist studios and spaces for small scale industry.

Argent, as developers and asset managers for the site, have developed the site as a thriving residential and commercial hub, visited by over 7 million people per year. Central to the place-making effort has been the delivery of over 70,000m² of public space, hosting a diverse range of uses, from major events, to community meetups, art installations and creative and cultural meanwhile uses. Argent's work with charity groups such as Global Generation has facilitated initiatives that have activated the site and provided opportunities for social connection and community building. The Kings Cross site is in the heart of the 'Knowledge Quarter' the name given to the area within a one-mile radius of King's Cross that provides a home to a cluster of +85 organisations spanning research, higher education, science, art, culture and media.

<https://www.kingscross.co.uk/>

<https://www.knowledgequarter.london>

Photo credits: John Sturrock

FRICHE LA BELLE DE MAI

Friche la Belle de Mai is located in the former Seita tobacco factory, an industrial brownfield site unused since 1980. The factory was redesigned and regenerated within the framework of "Marseille European Cultural Capital" in 2013. La Friche is settled in the 3rd district of Marseille and takes its name from the neighbourhood "Belle de Mai", one of the poorest districts of the city.

The factory has been transformed into a place of creativity and innovation - hosting 70 organisations on site, with 400 among artists and creatives who work there every day - as well as into a place for cultural dissemination and events - nearly 600 events each year, ranging from one off events to large-scale festivals. With over 400.000 visitors a year, la Friche is a multi-faceted public space comprising a sports area, a restaurant, 5 concert venues, shared gardens, a bookshop, a nursery, 2400 m² of exhibition space, 8000 m² of roof terrace and a training centre, all sustained by a diversified business model within a social cooperative organisation (SCIC - Société coopérative d'intérêt collectif).

<http://www.lafriche.org/en/>

Photo credits: Caroline Dutrey

MARSEILLE France

22@

22@ was initiated in 2000 in the Poblenou neighbourhood, the former manufacturing area of the city also known as the “Catalan Manchester” in the 19th century. The project aimed at redeveloping 1,159,626 m2 of industrial land and the potential creation of around 3,200,000 m2 of new construction. Involving the legal recognition of 4,614 already-existing homes and the construction of around 4,000 new subsidised units; 114,000 m2 of green area land. The goal was to preserve the productive character of the area through knowledge based and creative economy activities.

While preserving the industrial heritage, its redevelopment has been based on the support to the digital productive character of the territory, through the generation and installation of knowledge centres, companies and institutions, the development of a compact and complex city model, with mixed land use and citizen engagement, the implementation of an infrastructure plan to forge and consolidate the district as an advanced tertiary land, with the ultimate objective of fostering the conditions for the development of an open ecosystem of innovation. 22@ has become the epicentre of the start-up and co-working growth in the city. The district has been recently characterised by tactical urban design and planning strategies as in the case of the first super-block creation, in which traffic pacification and gain of public space have been addressed. The project has been revisited in 2018 through citizens’ participation process “repensem 22@” (rethinking22@) and the conversion of Poblenou in a makers district based on peer production and circular economy.

Photo credits: Alessio Patron

BARCELONA Spain

EC1 AND NEW CENTRE OF LODZ

EC1 Łódź - City of Culture is a revitalized and extended complex of the first Łódź power plant built in 1907. In the new Poland the Łódź power plant, 20% owned by the city, entered a new developmental phase, becoming part of the "Nowe Centrum Łódź" project, implemented by the City of Łódź since 2007. On May 15th, 2008 the City Council of Łódź established "EC1 Łódź - City of Culture" institution, supported by the Investment Bureau at the Department of Property Management of Łódź City Council. Renovation and modernisation of the post-industrial buildings was conducted, along with their conversion to new functions. Revitalisation took into account the importance and nature of the area, referring to the historical character of the buildings themselves.

The cubic volume, form, and most of the external features of the fronts, with their characteristic details, were maintained to retain their historical nature. The revitalised and expanded EC1 East complex now fulfils cultural, artistic and social functions. At the same time, it is an important element of the New Centre of Łódź, combining architectural trends from the previous century and cutting-edge post-industrial features. It is designed to be an open space for artists, fully adapted to host individual workshops and events. It is also a space for institutions organising cultural and educational events for the residents of Łódź.

<https://ec1lodz.pl>

Photo credits: www.lodz.pl

LODZ
Poland

RED TOWN

Shanghai Sculpture Space - known to the public as Red Town because of the colour of the bricks which gives the buildings a very distinctive appearance in the area - opened the door in 2005 in the industrial heritage of an early 20th century steel factory, which sat empty for years. It was first commissioned as a sculpture exhibition space with a very institutional drive, offering different shows organized by the Shanghai Urban Planning Bureau and Shanghai Sculpture Committee Office. It presented unique environmental features for a location downtown: versatile architecture spaces, open areas, grassy lawn facing an urban landscape, all of which contributed over the years to the structuring of a variety of activities and experiences, including art, leisure, and social functions.

It has been sustained with government funding (sculpture exhibitions) and private entrepreneurship; free of charge throughout its whole history until the closure in 2017, it was the stage of amusement for all the generation, in both formal and informal ways. Red Town has metamorphosed the 20th-century factory that formerly occupied this location from dusty and abandoned remnants to trendiest and peaceful creative "digs". On a total area of 18000 square meters, of which 11000 of business areas, 5000 of exhibitions, and 2000 of entertainment; it ultimately included a concert space (On Stage Live House), galleries, concert venues, fitness club, bridal couture boutique, art therapy studios, bookstores, organic cafes, floral markets, and vintage stores. Currently, a demolition and renovation project is underway. The large-scale remodeling project tore down most of the original Red Town, turning the new complex into the largest cultural, creative and commercial hub in central Shanghai. This new project is slated for completion by 2023.

Photo credits: Francesca Valsecchi

INDUSTRY CITY

In the 1890s Irving T. Bush began to build a monumental intermodal manufacturing, warehousing and distribution center in Sunset Park, Brooklyn. Due to its prominent location, immense scale, and structure that supported a wide spectrum of businesses, the site flourished. It quickly became one of the most successful facilities of its type, enabling Brooklyn to become a major international seaport. By the 1960s, urban manufacturing had started its long decline. Most of the major manufacturers closed their doors or moved away, and the area went through a period of disinvestment and decay for 40 years. In 2013, this all changed.

A new ownership group, led by Belvedere Capital and Jamestown, began to redevelop the site, laying the foundations for the creation of 'Industry City'. The project approached the 'innovation economy' as the umbrella term for redesigning and redeveloping the area around key objectives of new enterprise and jobs creation, high quality and environmental-friendly open spaces and buildings, and community facilities and amenities. A diversification of uses and sectors including research, cultural and creative industries, tech and digital manufacturing have allowed Industry City to create a vibrant and diverse community of forward-thinking companies, with jobs growing from 1,900 in 2013 to 8,000 in 2019.

<https://industrycity.com/>

Photo credits: Industry City

NEW YORK United States of America

“

Covid 19 is amplifying the visibility of pre-existing urban voids and emptying spaces that were already on their path towards new uses and meanings. Across Europe, thousands of regeneration sites are stopped and lose jobs and money everyday. At the same time, they are losing sight of what uses and functions might be in a post-pandemic scenario that we can hardly imagine.

We need more flexible and agile approaches to urban regeneration, and new ways to build cities around shared value and long term impact.

CAN MEANWHILE USES HAVE A STRATEGIC SAY IN THIS?

”

#SKIPGARDEN

Setting the scene

In the age of long emergencies and exacerbating inequalities, is there an alternative to the often rigid and extractive way in which we make urban regeneration? We argue there is.

We live in the midst of a global health crisis where cities are at the forefront of the emergency. During more than one year of prolonged lockdowns, our daily habits and ways of experiencing our cities have been changing radically, and yet we know little about the impacts on individual and collective health and wellbeing. We have been pushed to change, and increasingly the question is how we will get reacquainted with our cities *after*, with myriads of activities having disappeared, closed shutters, older generations partly erased and feelings of fear that won't likely fade away quickly.

Against Covid-19 and the context of climate breakdown and deep social change in which we live, **temporary uses are gaining momentum**. The pandemic is amplifying pre-existing risks and weaknesses, revealing the structural gaps in mainstream urban development paradigms rooted in globalised economies, gentrification-led

business models, privatisation of services, short termism, erosion of the commons and social trust. Increasingly, resilience is the keyword on top of recovery strategies, and temporary urbanism appears as a viable way to build back better, reconstructing alternative models that can unleash thriving and sustainable urban environments whilst mitigating against future shared risks. Major cities such as **London, Paris** and **Milan** - amongst many others - are currently regarding temporary uses as a key cornerstone to addressing the most pressing challenges of our times¹⁰.

Although we still lack a full understanding and systematization of meanwhile practices across Europe, these seem to grow relentlessly. New temporary initiatives are popping up here and there across cities, often from the initiative of grassroots movements, informal groups and civic activists. **Les Grands Voisins** in Paris, **See U** in Brussels, **Darwin** in Bordeaux are a few examples amidst a myriad of temporary projects that have settled in abandoned and decayed buildings and sites, transforming them rapidly into vibrant labs of creativity, civic engagement and social entrepreneurship. In **Berlin** - a pioneer in this field since the 90s - temporary uses have contributed to shape the vibe of entire quarters if not of the whole city, imprinting it with that underground and avantgard vein that has been attracting creatives, artists and *breakthroughers* from every corner of the globe. Spanning temporary shelters, artistic ateliers, cafés, activities in support to the elderly and marginalised communities or new entrepreneurship, temporary uses are showing

¹⁰ See: <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/progressingplanning/2020/07/06/meanwhile-uses-in-the-city-should-this-be-the-new-normal/>; https://www.c40knowledgehub.org/s/article/How-to-build-back-better-with-a-15-minute-city?language=en_US; <https://www.ilgiorno.it/milano/cronaca/negozi-vuoti-in-centro-s%C3%AC-ad-usi-temporanei-1.6029452>

versatility and capacity to engage with multiple needs. By giving new life to spaces designated for oblivion or market speculations, they help revert decay and abandonment, contrasting loss in property value. Furthermore, temporary uses are driving **new markets and professions**, particularly in the intermediation between demand and offer of spaces. **Meanwhile Spaces CIC**¹¹, **Plateau Urbain**¹², **ZZZ Zwischen - ZeitZentrale**¹³, **Urban Catalyst**¹⁴ are all examples of incumbents that show novel value propositions and business models for the management of vacant urban assets, often relying on social entrepreneurship forms, innovative public-private arrangements and on the integration of both 'hard' and 'soft' competencies of urban planning, design and placemaking. Lastly, as shown in a recent study by ARUP elaborated for the Greater London Authority¹⁵, the impact of temporary initiatives **often goes beyond the micro scale** at which they usually intervene, triggering catalytic effects over broader societal challenges such as the sustainability of food systems, community resilience, and climate change adaptation.

Covid 19 is amplifying pre-existing urban voids; temporary uses appear as a viable solution to contrast and revert this trend. Nonetheless, **the pandemic is also emptying spaces that were already on their path towards new uses and meanings, disrupting their visions, plans and investments**. Across Europe, thousands of

¹¹ <https://www.meanwhitespace.com/>

¹² <https://www.plateau-urbain.com/>

¹³ <https://www.zzz-bremen.de/>

¹⁴ See http://urbancatalyst.net/downloads/180820urban_catalyst-Final-documentation-2004.pdf

¹⁵ See: https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/meanwhile_use_for_london_final.pdf

regeneration sites are stuck and lose money every day, with cascading effects along the complex supply chain that characterises real estate. At the same time, **they are losing sight on what uses and positionings shall be in a post-pandemic scenario that we can hardly imagine.** If flexible and agile approaches to urban regeneration were *good to have* previously, they now become *must have*. And if goals of quality spaces were already mainstream within masterplans, we now urge higher ambitions that can redefine the right to the city around shared value and long term impact.

Can meanwhile uses have a strategic say in this?

In this Portfolio we capture highlights and stories of meanwhile uses from eight urban regeneration initiatives across Europe and beyond - i.e. **King's Cross** in London, **Manifattura Tabacchi** in Florence, **EC1** in Lodz, **22@** in Barcelona, **Dortmunder U and Union Quarter** in Dortmund, **Friche la Belle de Mai** in Marseille, **Industry City** in New York and **Red Town** in Shanghai. In **T-Factor**, these cases are the foundational source of knowledge and learning around meanwhile practices in urban regeneration, and they have initially inspired and triggered many of the assumptions and discovery paths that the project is willing to unfold.

These cases are largely diverse from each other, including in terms of consolidation, scale of intervention, types of spaces and assets to be regenerated, socio-cultural and economic characteristics of the areas, objectives addressed, impacts unfolding or achieved. Yet, what these initiatives have in common is the **adoption of**

meanwhile practices during what we call the waiting time in urban regeneration - that time period, usually complex and featured by construction and progressive spatial change - that stands between the approval of the masterplan or pre-masterplan on the one hand, and the delivery of the regenerated areas on the other hand. In this period, the temporary character of spaces is more or less determined at the outset, and it deals with a context where investors are specified, functions and positionings are outlined, and specific planning, construction and consultation procedures are at play.

Our spotlight is on spaces that are 'in waiting' - spaces that are waiting for a permanence that is more or less determined at the outset, and that face a context where investors are there, functions and positionings are outlined, and specific planning, construction and consultation procedures are at play. It's the waiting time in urban regeneration.

Applying temporary uses in the waiting time of urban regeneration can be strategic and beneficial for the different actors at stake. As this Portfolio will illuminate, multiple gains can be achieved, including higher quality spaces, enhanced participation, dialogue and trust, response to existing and emerging needs, new partnerships and collaborations, and revert feelings and perceptions of decay and abandonment. At the same time, to the extent that temporary uses unfold alongside the critical relationship between public and private interests, they can also cast shadows,

including around inclusion, appropriation of value, sustainability and legacy.

Meanwhile practices observed across the ACs seem to move relentlessly in this wide perimeter. There is **no unique model, but rather a multiplicity of strategies and approaches that take shape and evolve over time, from time to time unpacking and repacking interests, motivations, agendas and drivers.** They largely depart from a common need of more flexibility and adaptation in regeneration processes, and yet their paths unfold in different ways and unravel different impacts. There are both commonalities and specificities within a general understanding of meanwhile use as a more effective placemaking at the time of structural uncertainty, and as key levers to upgrade cities' software next to the hardware of physical infrastructures.

However, there may be a frontier that is yet to be marked. A frontier where meanwhile practices can become truly transformative, becoming **collective testbeds for novel 'regeneration codes' - governance, finance, regulation, culture, participation - geared toward co-benefits, shared value and long term impact. It is a meanwhile designed and orchestrated by emergence to scaffold new transitions, unlocking collective imagination, agency and legitimacy to change cities toward a preferred future.**

If none of the ACs may be fully positioned on this frontier already, they may nonetheless show seeds and signs of this transformative potential, and thus make the case for the latter to be accelerated and scaled up across European cities.

Portfolio framework

INFRASTRUCTURING BY CHOREOGRAPHY OF MEANWHILE USES

In this section of the Portfolio, we briefly illustrate the framework that has loosely guided and informed the mapping and clustering of insights and findings across the ACs. The framework is not descriptive of a precise model. Rather, it is a 'mind map' initially built on the basis of the key concepts that inform the T-Factor project (where *infrastructuring in system dynamics* stands as a guiding one), and further iterated over time through ongoing analysis and reflection.

Findings and highlights are reported in the pages that follow, according to the three infrastructuring emphases or dimensions – strategic, operational, relational - described above. Importantly, many of the findings could be read and interpreted through all these three emphases; however, they have been associated with the one(s) where they appeared to be more relevant.

In the last section of the document, the framework also guides our final reflections and conclusions around transformative meanwhile practices in urban regeneration.

Framework pillars

#Choreography of meanwhile uses

Across the ACs, multiple meanwhile initiatives have been emerging over time in response to different objectives and needs, opportunities and challenges. Single meanwhile initiatives might be less or more significant in the wider scale and scope of the regeneration process in which they take place. Yet, when considered all together, they can start to unfold a deep change in the way people perceive a place and begin to interact with it. It is the '**choreography of meanwhile uses**' at stake here, and how it has been strategically applied or acknowledged by emergence, and further managed over time alongside the regeneration process.

#Infrastructuring choreographies of meanwhile uses

Steering and orchestrating meanwhile practices in urban regeneration is more than an enabling action. In T-Factor, we understand it as a process of **infrastructuring**: *an intentional action of providing the means for experimentation, discovery and learning within a steering and coordination framework that supports both present and future collaborations* (Thorpe and Manzini, 2018). Under this perspective, infrastructuring meanwhile

practices in urban regeneration can be understood as a **continuous weaving and scaffolding path** that operates at different scales and scopes and with different emphasis including:

Strategic: focused on the role of meanwhile uses within broader plans of redevelopment and regeneration and their capacity to support alignment between public and private agendas. This strategic aspect, in the context of this Portfolio, essentially looks at the way meanwhile uses, across the ACs, have been emerging, framed and applied in the process of accommodating both the 'short' term masterplan goals and the longer term objectives and ambitions of city regeneration.

Operational: focused on operational levers - organisation, management, regulation, funding, etc. - that allow meanwhile practices to exist as systemic processes.

Relational: focused on quality and value generated through meanwhile interventions. This relational aspect, in the context of the Portfolio, essentially looks at the way meanwhile uses have been applied to unlock "software" upgrades and rewiring, including in terms of relational capital and social trust, engagement and collaboration and capacity building.

Building on (Thorpe & Manzini, 2018; Manzini 2015; Le Dantec and Di Salvo 2011; Bjorgvinsson et al. 2010), we assume 'infrastructuring' as our guiding concept in the Portfolio - and in the broader **T-Factor** project - in its potential to capture some of the key characteristics of temporary use practices in urban regeneration, including:

- Their **processual and evolutive** dimension within a system which is first of all relational.

- Their inner nature of 'learning by doing' processes that **emerge from people in practice**.
- Their activation by means of '**multiple designing networks or coalitions**' that can be intentionally connected to influence each other and thus influence the overall results, in a process that can also be conflictual.
- An activation that can accommodate both **short and long term objectives** of urban regeneration and that is loosely designed and managed to facilitate the **emergence of new temporary uses and practices along the way**.

In the context of the Portfolio, more than a descriptive concept, 'infrastructuring' has been used as a reference for reflection and discussion around the way meanwhile uses, across the ACs, have been orchestrated with different degrees of intentionality, and how such an orchestration has been supportive in the achievement of different benefits and impacts.

#System dynamics and co-benefits across hardware and software

Across the ACs, different types of levers - strategic, operational or relational - have been activated and connected in different ways. Meanwhile uses exist and develop within urban systems, inherently characterised by interdependencies across both 'hardware' elements such as physical infrastructures and assets and more immaterial or 'software' elements such as social relations and culture. The way these levers are linked and the extent to which connectivity runs across the system form the path towards direct benefits, co-benefits and impacts. It is the DNA of meanwhile uses towards regeneration legacy.

PORTFOLIO FRAMEWORK

SPILLOVER EFFECTS

INDIRECT CO-BENEFITS

DIRECT CO-BENEFITS

/RELATIONAL

Exploring the role of temporary uses in unlocking sustainable and long term thriving regeneration outcomes

- Relational capital
- Trust
- Capacity building
- Collaboration
- Co-creation
- Agency & Legitimacy

/OPERATIONAL

Exploring the role of temporary uses towards enhancing the effectiveness of the regeneration process

- Regulation
- Team
- Funding
- Organisation
- Monitoring & Evaluation

/STRATEGIC

Exploring the role of temporary uses towards enhancing the value of the masterplan

- Masterplan
- Orchestration of Meanwhile Uses
- Partnerships
- Urban planning culture
- Emergence of Meanwhile Uses

HIGHLIGHTS

Strategic Highlights

In this section of the Portfolio, we look at how meanwhile uses, across the ACs, have been unlocked to respond to strategic objectives of urban development.

More in particular, we report on highlights and stories related to the relationship of temporary uses with masterplans and regeneration objectives, interrogating the way in which these practices have emerged, how they have been understood and framed, and how they have been taking shape alongside masterplans' goals and longer term ambitions of city regeneration.

Public-Private Partnerships

The large majority of the ACs are characterised by **regeneration partnerships where both public and private actors are actively involved**. Vis-à-vis redevelopments that are increasingly risky and cumbersome, PPPs are emerging as a distinctive character of urban regeneration, standing as a critical engine for better alignment between public and private players. Temporary uses within the business strategy for the development appear as a viable way to unleash mitigation effects, especially when it comes to the fear that citizens may feel with respect to regeneration projects, and the risks of losing access to spaces.

The redevelopment of **Dortmunder U and Union Quarter** rooted in a **public-private partnership based on integrated, multi-departmental cooperation**. This allowed the redevelopment to incorporate economic, ecological, urban planning, cultural and social considerations within the regeneration strategy. Such an integrated arrangement was not common at that time and required learning by doing for more than 10 years; the ongoing support of decision makers at different governmental levels (City Mayor on top) turned out to be key in unlocking integrated regeneration outcomes. The **Rheinische Straße consultation group** accompanied the implementation, supplemented by specialist groups on the subjects of real estate management, work, trade and retail, social infrastructure, immigration, education and culture.

During the 1990's a more business-oriented culture had entered government, and joint public/private ventures were the preferred way forward particularly in complex redevelopments. The establishment of the **King's Cross Partnership (KXP)** - including the Boroughs of Camden and Islington, Railtrack, London & Continental Railways, Argent, community representatives and other public bodies - has been key in bringing forward negotiations and consultations for a redevelopment that had seen strong local opposition and aborted schemes. It was crucial that the development team could work in close collaboration with Camden Council and the local community.

In the transformation of **Red Town** in Shanghai different public-private partnerships have run alongside the history of the place. The original masterplan intended to privatize the land in the most profitable way, yet the way in which this process unfolded changed throughout different generation of estate and administrative norms: first, industrial land become cultural (the introduction of Sculpture Park and the museum), then it became commercial, opening to office rentals and leisure tenants. Land prices continued to rise, changing the nature of the site from cultural to more commercial spaces and offices. Independent art galleries or small young creatives left the place in favor of international studios or companies. The dynamic of the PPP was therefore fluid.

Learnings

The public player is less and less able to take on high-risk interventions. PPP makes it possible to implement a good combination of the private sector and the community sector, unleashing opportunities of working together, with architects, designers and facilitators working on the interface to make it happen.

Public authority, Developer

Flexible Masterplans and agile regeneration processes

Particularly in the case of large scale and long term renovations, meanwhile uses often come with the need of accommodating more flexible and agile masterplanning and delivery. Rather than a plan for rigid and deterministic functions, a flexible masterplan is a loosely designed framework that can evolve over time, building through **sprints and sequences**. In this context, meanwhile uses generally emerge as a strategic way to **better understand the context of intervention before delivering on permanent uses and functions**. Flexibility may not only relate to uses and functions, but rather embrace the other key components of regeneration strategies, including visions, positionings, themes addressed, target groups, in the first instance.

The regeneration of **King's Cross** is one of the biggest masterplan development projects ever undertaken in London. What is often referred to as its 'flexible' masterplan was designed around a framework of permanent streets and squares, and changeable city blocks. Argent, the developer, recognised that an 'end state' masterplan, where everything is designed at the beginning, was too inflexible; instead, a masterplan had to be capable of being built **in different configurations and sequences**. This meant that individual components choreographed successfully could add significant value early on, and adapt to unexpected changes to the social, economic and political situation. Central to their proposal was to **safeguard time for an extensive dialogue with local politicians and communities** in order to achieve a robust proposal. At the time this went against the standard approach by developers which was to assemble a professional team and produce designs without prior discussion with the local communities.

The regeneration of **EC1 and the new city centre in Lodz** understood flexible masterplanning and phasing as the way to make plans and deliveries more realistic, citizen-centered and connected to small scale urban cultures. **Testing options** and supporting **wide consultations with communities** have been key to provide a framework for the whole redevelopment. Flexible masterplanning also meant overcoming **overly detailed masterplans** that could become outdated quickly.

Both **Friche** and **Manifattura Tabacchi's** masterplans have undergone multiple transformations to unlock evolving connotations of

culture. Arts, culture and creativity are at the heart of both redevelopments: **meanwhile uses have been strategically applied to experiment with multiple crossovers between arts, design, making, tech, science and nature, and to deliver on permanent uses more flexibly and iteratively**. At **La Friche**, the various masterplans designed over time have worked mainly as inspirational guidelines premised on the central role of artists and artistic production in driving vibrant and inclusive placemaking.

Learnings

*Even within flexible masterplans, there needs to be a **rigorous attention to phasing**. This enables partners to understand what spaces are available for meanwhile uses and when, and this in turn allows the latter to better develop and grow. The phasing design must be carried out in close collaboration with the contractors.*

Developer

*Developers tend to be quite risk averse and therefore any projects which might influence the perception of the area might be carefully scrutinised, implying a rigidity in the way meanwhile uses are taken into account. These can have higher chances to be actively supported when they are **deliberately designed to encourage developers to take on more risks**.*

Developer, Meanwhile Orchestrator, Meanwhile practitioner, Public authority

Established meanwhile culture, developers' intuition or by serendipity: emergence of meanwhile uses

Across the ACs, only a few renovations have been developing within planning cultures and policy frameworks that incorporate temporary use practices. Where this is not the case, meanwhile strategies seem to stem **primarily from the intuition and previous experience of developers in other contexts**, which in turn helped tackle and overcome regulatory barriers and grey zones in licencing, security and liability regimes.

German planning culture plays an important role in the way meanwhile uses are understood and implemented across the country. In **Dortmund**, they explicitly form the backbone of the city-making strategy and are included in German planning strategies, programs and projects as part of the National Urban Development Policy. It is also worth highlighting that in the redevelopment of the Union Quarter, the **Agency for New Use** ("Agentur für Neue Nutzungen") was established as one of 29 planned interventions, with the specific goal of fostering vacancy management in the area and give

impetus to new ideas for existing vacancies.

At **Manifattura Tabacchi**, meanwhile uses came from the **intuition of the developer vis-à-vis the lack of a consolidated meanwhile culture in the city and more broadly in the country**. Temporary uses in the regeneration project proved to be a **novel and inspiring practice for the Municipality and other local stakeholders**, witnessed by wide interest and attempts to replicate the approach in other regeneration contexts, including in other Italian cities.

Meanwhile uses have also emerged in the run within **public realm strategies**, mainly as a way to respond to **emerging needs or to counteract negative effects** brought about by construction periods. On the other hand, they have also emerged as **forms of protest and opposition to redevelopments**.

Whilst the terms 'meanwhile' and 'temporary use' were not common during the time that the **King's Cross** development was being planned in the early 2000's, there was a **recognition of the values that arts and culture could bring, and specific mechanisms designed to activate the site early on**. Meanwhile projects were quite emergent also thanks to the openness of the developer to new ideas. Argent ended up spending more than originally estimated in the activation strategy, because it made commercial and political sense.

In the case of **22@**, temporary use mainly emerged from the bottom up, often as **forms of protest and opposition**. For example, **Can Ricart** - a formerly

abandoned industrial complex - hosts today a Youth Centre where many youth associations and residents in Poblenou convene together. Can Ricart has been promoted by a grassroots movement that mobilized against the redevelopment: neighbours protested around the lack of social housing and the absence of community facilities. These conflicts led to a rethinking of the masterplan with more social housing and community facilities such as a public library.

In the case of **Dortmunder U and Union Quarter**, meanwhile uses such as the **Blue House, Café U-Jack and ProjectGarden** were planned at early stages. However, there were a few unintended meanwhile uses that emerged along the way. For example, the **Skate Park Utopia** emerged from a synergy between the City government and the youth association Skateboard Initiative. No longer being able to skate at the front forecourt of the U, skateboarders began skating on the stairs located at the back of the U, which faced the empty lot that would become the skate park. The synergy was created when the City approached the Skateboard Initiative with the offer of using the empty lot.

Furthermore, meanwhile practices have also taken shape through **'serendipity', especially where the waiting time is understood and deliberately orchestrated as an experimental and discovery period** for more or less permanent uses, functions and meanings.

La Friche is the emblematic case of meanwhile uses that emerge by serendipity. There is no

meanwhile strategy as such, but rather a "practice of meanwhile" that is deeply embedded in the management of the whole site. It is a **permanent meanwhile** under experimentation for more than 30 years, where temporary uses continuously emerge, develop, get consolidated or fade away as a means of continuous invention of new points of view and interactions with the site. This also reflects a broader approach within public authorities across France, where meanwhile uses often derive from funding programmes that support artistic experimentation.

Degrees of flexibility and strategic application: orchestration of temporary uses

Meanwhile uses in urban regeneration can be applied with different strategic intents and degrees of flexibility. Across the ACs, **no one single model emerges but rather multiple geometries of intents and applications** that take shape at the beginning depending on contextual factors, and that further along the way hand in hand with ongoing opportunities and challenges. Yet, from the analysis of the ACs we can depict **three, non-mutually exclusive 'macro' approaches**:

- /Marketing & Attraction
- /Engagement & Reactivation
- /Masterplan Testbed

/Marketing and attraction

Especially in the case of meanwhile strategies deliberately planned at the outset, these follow a strategic goal of attraction and establishment of direct dialogue and relationship with local communities, institutions, and citizens at large. Temporary uses are **pivotal in building location and destination brands**, as they help create fresh and lively site images that can particularly attract young people, creatives, and innovative enterprises. In this respect, arts, culture and creativity usually stand as strategic levers, with different entanglements between arts, culture and redevelopments' business models.

Summer 2018 marked the first year of meanwhile activation at **Manifattura Tabacchi**. Temporary uses have been developed with the specific goal of raising wide interest around the site, which until that moment had remained closed for 17 years. Only the former workers and senior generations had memories of it; therefore, there was the need to unveil its aura of mystery. Summer 2018 developed several temporary initiatives involving the former workers, with events targeted at families and local communities and conceived as **calls to action for re-imagining the future of the place**.

The overall strategy for **EC1** was to leave the site open to visitors during the period of construction,

which was strategically phased to allow different parts of the site to be used at different times. Since 2007, EC1 has been hosting several events that proved to be successful in attracting residents and visitors. Events were usually organised by NGOs and local institutions and **connected to broader cultural events and festivals in Łódź with a well-established reputation**.

One of the public engagement strategies at **Industry City** was to create **immersive art installations** for visitors and tenants to enjoy. These often became "**Instagrammable moments**" and initiated a dialogue between the urban dwellers and the Art, to generate moments or images that people would want to share via social media. The marketing strategy behind the rebranding of the area was to harvest individual stories to change the dialogue and a new perspective on an otherwise rarely seen as attractive area of the city.

In 2002, the decision of the University of the Arts London to relocate their main campus in the North of King's Cross brought Argent to shift the focus of the development **from a financial centre towards a creative centre**. This tied in with the rise of the creative and tech sectors in London in the early 2000's. The decision paved the way for the other creative and tech uptake on building plots in the area, now including **Facebook, Google and Universal amongst others**.

The evolution of **Red Town** is based on "points of attraction". By placing contemporary sculpture in the open spaces of the old architectural core of the warehouse, the intention was to set a public

space within a private land, which is an unusual operation in the frame of urban development. In fact, what more often happens is that there are lots of private or "enclosed" zones in the official public place: taking the example of parks, most of the grass is not accessible, it can only be "seen from aside". In the case of Sculpture Park, it was the opposite: sculptures **were places all around the area**, and the park was open 24h a day with no restrictions.

Branding, marketing and attraction-led meanwhile strategies are also key across the ACs led by the public sector, **especially when they tie in with international labels and awards such as the 'European Capital of Culture'**. These are significant boosts in changing perceptions and urban identities, as well as in fostering adaptable transformation of spaces.

A major milestone for La Friche happened in 2013, when **Marseille was awarded as European Capital of Culture**. Thanks to the funding and a strong political willingness to integrate arts and culture in the City, the site was improved and expanded, reinforcing the idea that any space can be modulated and accommodate new uses hand in hand with emerging opportunities.

The renovation of **Dortmunder U** began as one of the flagship projects for the **RUHR.2010 European Capital of Culture**. Dortmund U was rehabilitated due to its landmark status and with the goal of turning it into a **centre for arts, culture and creativity**, in the overall attempt to reinvent the meaning of this iconic site. The renovation of Dortmund U and the Ruhr region's appointment

as European Capital of Culture are also linked to the regeneration of several quarters throughout Dortmund, among them Rheinische Straße - **rebranded as Union Quarter.**

/Engagement & Reactivation

Across the majority of the ACs, temporary uses have served and sustained processes of site reactivation. Especially where temporary uses have been applied intentionally or 'acknowledged' over time by developers, these are largely understood as **more effective forms of public engagement** that can make redevelopments closer to **both existing and emerging needs**, be they related for example to affordable spaces for artistic production, upskilling & reskilling, or to the need of addressing stress and tensions in residents forced to be temporarily relocated elsewhere. At the same time, collaborative placemaking via temporary uses is most often understood and strategically approached as a way to **change negative perceptions more quickly.**

The **Lighthouse Keepers and area hosts** is an initiative by the **City of Lodz** aimed at providing a comprehensive answer to the complex problems of residents that are temporarily relocated during construction periods; for many of them, this can bring about psychological stress and result in feelings of loss and resistance. In order to increase their sense of security and alleviate the difficulties generated by the move, this initiative aimed at facilitating residents' access to knowledge about revitalisation measures, monitoring the process of adaptation to the new location and reducing tensions.

The **QuarterCafé U-Jack** in Dortmund was established as a new neighbourhood meeting place and developed in close collaboration with the city's Job Centre. The idea was to introduce **long-term unemployed people** to the occupational fields of service, cooking and housekeeping. The initiative is still in place, targeting in particular disadvantaged families and children.

Temporary initiatives such as **B9 at Manifattura Tabacchi** or **Relay Arts Programme in King's Cross** emerged from the need of providing young artists, makers and designers with **more affordable spaces for creative expression**, while leveraging artistic and cultural production as ways to change negative perceptions. B9 is experimenting with contemporary arts, design and maker manufacturing to attract and sustain a creative community at Manifattura Tabacchi, combining ateliers, thematic laboratories and makerspaces where temporary tenants are all creatives of the Florentine landscape. Similarly, the **Relay Arts Programme** at King's Cross has consisted of a careful curation of public arts initiatives that involved both local curators and international artists, as a way to change negative perceptions (particularly in terms of safety and lack of amenities) around the site, allowing King's Cross to be perceived as a destination in itself.

Ambition in engagement and issues intended to be addressed are also key ingredients in the choice of temporary uses: from strategies particularly oriented to social or cultural uses (for example around unemployment, upskilling and reskilling, isolation and loneliness), passing through **sports and leisure uses**, up to **commercial and entrepreneurship uses**. Nonetheless, **mixité in**

temporary uses is a recurring character of many of the ACs, which may also originate from the **mixité in permanent functions envisaged in the masterplans**. Furthermore, with mixed temporary uses comes a rich typology of spaces utilized for temporary activities, which often includes vacant plots, industrial buildings, warehouses, hangars and outdoor spaces.

Within the umbrella of the 'innovation economy', **Industry City** has deliberately approached meanwhile activation as a way to achieve multiple impacts, including in terms of jobs and enterprise creation, improvements in mobility and energy efficient buildings, quality public facilities. Meanwhile activation has run through mixed uses, **combining job, community and environmental programming to bring different communities back to the site, overall contributing to higher quality private and public spaces.**

There have been a wide range of carefully curated meanwhile uses and activation strategies at **King's Cross** developed over the course of 21 years. These range from **arts and culture programming, to one-off cultural events, to more community focussed projects, and larger public realm events, and more commercially focussed meanwhile**. Many of these projects have been developed in close collaboration with other stakeholders but for the most part carefully orchestrated by the developer.

/Masterplan testbed

A fewer ACs are characterised by an approach to temporary uses as **testbeds for design hypotheses.**

In these cases, temporary uses go beyond “software” activities, prototyping permanent uses at small and rapidly implementable scales. Some examples include prototyping of temporary artist studios, making facilities, “unconventional” museums, community gardens, cafés. Usually, such an experimental approach also **helps introduce innovative themes aligned with broader city strategies and policies** related for example to healthy lifestyles, urban greening, youth entrepreneurship in cultural and creative sectors. Moreover, testbed approaches usually come with **nomadic approaches to spaces**, which strategically allow manoeuvring within construction periods in order to progressively unveil spaces’ potential in light of permanent uses.

The temporary project **B9 at Manifattura Tabacchi** has been conceived as the **prototype of the contemporary civic centre, anticipating what the permanent Factory** - where all the creative energies activated will finally find a home - will look like. B9 has a prototyping role in the sense that the final project intends to **stabilize successful temporary uses such as artist and makers studios**. B9 created the opportunity for the property to get in contact with potential future tenants, testing the initial hypothesis.

King’s Cross Skip Garden developed from the idea of using skips as moveable planters. Between 2009 and 2019 the Skip Garden had **four different locations** across the King’s Cross development site with the final location closing in 2019. The Skip Garden was designed to be moveable in

acknowledgement that the phasing of the sites at King’s Cross meant that vacant land would be available at different times throughout the regeneration process. The nomadic approach allowed the Skip Garden to be agile enough to respond to changing conditions on the ground.

The nomadic use of spaces is at the heart of the way **La Friche** experiments with new functions and meanings. **‘Empty spaces’** is the term defining spaces purposely left vacant throughout the site, that mostly embody the historical symbolism of the factory. These spaces can be used for different purposes (exhibition venues, storage, music events, performances). This makes it possible to experiment with new forms of collaboration, generating new perspectives on possible uses and functions, stimulating freedom in creativity, and triggering new thematic crossovers. These spaces are widely considered and managed as **urban commons**.

Learnings

Real estate priorities often set and determine the character and ambition of meanwhile strategies. These may have higher chances to inform development plans if they fully incorporate developers’ priorities. This does not mean serving their interest only; instead, this can become the ground to better understand when and how, along the way, there are higher chances for negotiation between public and private interests.

Developer, Public authority, Meanwhile Orchestrator

Targeted meanwhile strategies can facilitate design and management; nevertheless, especially when target groups change over time, this may imply the risk of vanishing efforts. A more holistic way of dealing with different target groups can better foster inclusive engagement and deliver on positive outcomes incrementally.

Meanwhile Orchestrator

Software vs Hardware.

Investing in soft temporary activities only can limit attraction and experimentation. Giving equal attention to ‘hardware’, for example by creating temporary making facilities equipped with materials and working tools, can be a powerful lever of inclusion, especially in contexts where these types of spaces are not affordable nor easily accessible.

Meanwhile practitioner

Operational Highlights

In this section of the Portfolio, we explore findings and insights related to the way meanwhile uses have been operationalised and set in place across the ACs.

More in detail, we look at aspects such as organisation, team and management, governance, monitoring and evaluation, regulation and funding.

In-house, outsourcing and mixed schemes

Especially when meanwhile uses are activated at scale and planned from the very beginning, early design of proper organisational arrangements stand as a crucial aspect. **In house, outsourcing or hybrid schemes are all options that have been applied**, from case to case depending on the nature of the development (public or private led), expertise available, existing urban planning culture, as well as the intended scale and scope of meanwhile activation.

At **Manifattura Tabacchi**, the property outsourced the design and management of the meanwhile strategy to an external company - LAMA Agency. LAMA was approached by the property based on its experience with collaborative placemaking gained through Impact Hub Florence, LAMA's coworking and lab for social innovation. For the meanwhile strategy at MT, LAMA created a controlled company - Made in Manifattura (MIM), in order to ensure better accountability and effective management of both budget and strategy. MIM does not operate in full autonomy, but rather following annual strategic directions provided by the developer.

In **King's Cross**, the developer opted for an in-house approach, retaining the design and management of the activation strategy. The placemaking programme was loosely organised around three strands - arts, events and community - and managed internally.

Regenerations at **Dortmunder U and Union Quarter** and **EC1 in Lodz** applied mixed public-private schemes. They followed an **integrated and multi-stakeholder approach**, involving expertise across multiple departments as well as investors, contractors, citizens and local cultural associations, including youth associations.

Learnings

Intermediaries as Community builders.

Meanwhile activation is essentially a community-building process and requires expertise and capacity to design and set in place proper engagement, facilitation, matchmaking and networking methods and tools. However, this also poses a question on sustainability once temporary uses are over and there is no plan to keep facilitation in place.

Meanwhile Orchestrator

Multidisciplinary teams

Meanwhile activation strategies usually require structured teams that can embrace the various skills and expertise needed in urban regeneration. Across many ACs we can observe a clear attempt to

integrate the two key domains - urban planning and urban regeneration - usually at stake in redevelopments, in order to overcome siloed ways of working. Moreover, many teams seem to follow an "accordion" process, growing or shrinking hand in hand with the specific character and scale of temporary uses implemented from time to time. Nevertheless, there are recurring competencies and skills domains, including in **programme design, community building, communication and marketing, space design and artistic direction and curation**.

The core team of MIM, the company managing the meanwhile strategy at Manifattura Tabacchi, combines skills including **communication and marketing, event management, community engagement and space design**. The team has been growing over time to incorporate specific expertise, especially in artistic and cultural production. In the second year of temporary activation - which marked the full opening of MT with activities and events on a daily basis - the core team enrolled up to 15 persons. An important aspect has also been the active involvement of **cultural and artistic specialists known internationally as advisors**.

Placemaking in **King's Cross** has been managed by a **dedicated internal team within Argent**, which soon realised the need of professional input and set up an **Arts Advisory Panel** in 2009, employing specialist curators, and an artist in residence programme, established in partnership with the Arts Council.

In Łódź, a **specific masters programme** was

created to address the tensions and dysfunctional cooperation between technical and social teams that worked in the NCL regeneration project. The aim of the programme is to **create professionals able to work with a holistic approach to urban regeneration**. The master combines technical and humanistic knowledge from six scientific disciplines (architecture, construction, sociology, educational sciences, geography, spatial planning, economics, and management).

Learnings

Clear, good and context specific communication with the different actors at stake is key to manage expectations and mitigate possible tensions. The scope and nature of meanwhile uses should be clarified from the beginning, especially when they could entail noise and high flows of people, or when landlords may expect economic benefits from temporary rents.

A multi-disciplinary team and expertise in co-creation may not be enough. Often, the **property owner's willingness and readiness to experiment and test makes the difference**. Temporary uses should be deliberately made to create capacities and new mindsets in developers and local authorities.

Meanwhile Orchestrator, Developers

Governance: top-down, bottom up or *in between*

Meanwhile uses have an intrinsic multi-stakeholder nature - they exist within a fundamental relational dimension, which can unfold through various degrees of collaboration and synergies. **There is great variety in governance models across the ACs**, depending on 'who' drives the redevelopment and meanwhile activation, the existing urban planning and participation culture, types of actors involved, etc. Yet, despite this diversity, **temporary uses are often acknowledged as powerful catalysts for collaborative placemaking**, which in turn unfold **via various degrees of ownership, agency and legitimacy across the various temporary initiatives considered, and in respect to their overall orchestration**.

In **Manifattura Tabacchi**, the governance structure builds on **'check and balance' principles** between the property and the company that runs meanwhile activation. The former stands on top of the decision-making process, with the responsibility of developing the permanent project; the latter is responsible for temporary activities according to the strategic directions given by the developer. Despite this relatively top-down structure, MIM is particularly characterised by co-creation approaches. The activation strategy has shifted over time from self-produced activities, to an on-demand approach that hosts activities proposed and curated by

others, up to a **platform approach** - still under experimentation - in which MIM is seeking to fully enable wide co-production.

Dortmunder U and Union Quarter's renovation has followed a very flexible and dynamic governance. Especially at the beginning, public engagement was geared towards the close involvement of the district actors. Some of the working groups that were created still exist today. Consultation group meetings comprised **stakeholders from various city departments, policy makers, civil society organisations, landlords, businesses and citizens at large**. About 60 people joined the meetings regularly, and this was key in **reconnecting top-down and bottom-up structures** in such a way that people knew each other. There were no particular methods for these meetings. The flexibility and creativity of the Mayor proved to be key in fostering participation.

In **King's Cross**, the decisions on the types of meanwhile projects to develop mainly came from the developer, who, to a certain extent controlled most aspects of what happened on the site also to maintain a coordinated image. However, the wide array of meanwhile projects occurring at King's Cross were usually developed in cooperation with and in response to the demands of the various stakeholders engaged, such as local businesses, residents, local institutions or community groups

La Friche embraces stakeholder collaboration and distributed ownership through a cooperative legal form - **Société Coopérative d'Intérêt Collectif (SCIC)** - organised into **three colleges (residents/**

proximity/contributors) that bring together users, cultural operators and public institutions on its board of directors. This collaborative management system, which is atypical in France for a project of this scale, was chosen in order to allow the expansion of a cohesive community within the city. Via the SCIC legal status, La Friche seeks to fully enable the **urban commons**, based on the willingness of all the actors involved to build a shared project.

The **Pla Buits (Empty Spaces)** Programme initiated in 2012 by the City of Barcelona clearly exemplifies an *'in between'* governance framework which is steered and coordinated by the City, but where wide engagement is enabled through open calls to vacant (public) sites reactivation. The Programme has been key to sustaining a variety of temporary projects in different fields - sports, urban farming and agriculture, circus, arts and culture, education – and across different neighbourhoods of the city.

Learnings

Collaborative governance often deals with decision-making dynamics that can become long and complicated. This may paradoxically create disengagement and mistrust, and erode the key preconditions for collaboration. Structuring flexible and changeable decision 'platforms' - for example via thematic working groups that involve representatives of different

meanwhile uses - may help create clearer dynamics of collaboration and contribute to wider agency and legitimacy.

**Meanwhile Orchestrator,
Meanwhile practitioners, Beneficiary**

Well-structured governance arrangements do not necessarily unlock collaboration. Often, it is the **management culture and style** that makes the difference, and how it takes shape in everyday conversations and ways of engaging with people

Meanwhile Orchestrator

Monitoring and Evaluating temporary uses

Monitoring and evaluation are key aspects that allow to better seize the effectiveness of meanwhile uses vis-à-vis the set strategies. Moreover, they stand as a **fundamental source of storytelling and reporting towards stakeholders and citizens**. Monitoring and evaluation apply to different extents and via different tools and methods in the various ACs, with more relevance for the cases that have deliberately opted for meanwhile activation as part of the regeneration strategy. In these latter cases, the types of indicators are similar, including outreach and attraction, diversity in target groups involved,

levels of appreciation and satisfaction, retention, collaborations activated, in the first instance. Indeed, from the perspective of both developers and 'meanwhile intermediaries', these indicators are often crucial to make more informed decisions in the subsequent steps of implementation.

Although commissioned by the developer itself, implying a possible conflict of interest, an **impact assessment of the King's Cross development** was published in 2017¹⁶, analysing impacts across economic, social and financial domains. However, an impact assessment on the disadvantaged communities surrounding the site has not been implemented. Monitoring and evaluation also applied to individual meanwhile uses; for example, in the case of the **King's Cross Construction Skills Centre**, performance is monitored on a **monthly basis**.

The final evaluation of the Rheinische Strasse urban redevelopment examines the changes that have taken place in the **Union Quarter**. The aim was to analyse the successes and obstacles of individual projects as well as the impact of the whole redevelopment. The process consisted of statistical monitoring, expert discussions with actors from the neighbourhood, and meetings with the project team. In addition, the results of a 2015 survey targeting residents and visitors were included.

In **Manifattura Tabacchi**, a structured impact evaluation has not occurred yet. However, MIM -

¹⁶ "The Economic and Social Story of King's Cross", A Final Report, Regeneris Consulting, November 2017.

the company running meanwhile activation - has continuously **monitored performance indicators** (outreach, revenues, social media analytics) of the various meanwhile initiatives implemented over time, also producing **a large documentation for each event organized**. This has helped, on the one hand, to communicate and promote the results achieved, and on the other hand, to better inform ongoing decisions and programming.

Learnings

Holistic impact evaluation is key to measuring and assessing the contribution of meanwhile uses in urban regeneration, and it should acknowledge their processual and mostly qualitative nature. It shouldn't be limited to direct beneficiaries and communities on site, but also interrogate effects and impacts over surrounding areas. Participatory and inclusive methodologies should be preferred, considering the full range of diverse actors and stakeholders at stake, with priority on vulnerable and marginalised communities. Moreover, impact measurement should consider and integrate socio-cultural, economic and environmental aspects.

Additionality of temporary uses. Temporary uses in urban regeneration bring about multiple added values; yet, 'isolating' such values from broader regeneration outcomes is not an easy task. Evaluation and impact assessment should therefore consider 'contribution' rather than 'attribution aspects', and do so with a systemic lens - i.e. inquiring whether and how temporary uses stand as

mechanisms for reinforcing loops of change in urban regeneration.

*Public authority,
Meanwhile Orchestrator,
Meanwhile practitioner*

Established regulatory frameworks or grey zones

Regulatory frameworks on meanwhile uses are quite underdeveloped across the majority of the ACs, confirming that these practices are still on their way towards consolidation and recognition. However, when such regulatory frameworks are in place, they stand as **important levers that can allow better design and planning, as well as more effective investment in meanwhile activation and in turn in urban regeneration**. Moreover, meanwhile uses often confront themselves with complex policy and regulatory frameworks related to broader urban planning and regeneration that may directly affect and inform their emergence, design and management.

Section 106 is a legal agreement between an applicant seeking planning permission and the

local planning authority, used to mitigate the impact of developments on the local community and infrastructure. For **King's Cross**, a Section 106 was signed off between the developer and the local planning authority, marking a stepping stone in the whole redevelopment process. A key focus within the agreement was on **improving education and creating apprenticeships** and employment opportunities **for residents living adjacent to the site**, suffering particularly from deprivation. It proved to be a key point of leverage for supporting financially meanwhile activation at King's Cross, as in the case of the **King's Cross Construction Skills Centre**.

In Dortmund, some meanwhile interventions can be found in projects deriving from the program **"Experimental City and Residential Development"**, which belongs to the Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Home Affairs (BMI) and is supervised by the Federal Institute for Building, Urban and Spatial Research (BBSR) in the Federal Office for Building and Regional Planning (BBR). This programme seeks to promote innovative planning measures in urban development and housing. Importantly, **meanwhile uses are not explicitly differentiated from long-term uses in law. Nonetheless, regulatory documents such as building and planning codes, and leasing measures do provide an implicit framework that compartmentalise the requirements for long-term and temporary uses.**

The presence of a clearly defined framework for operationalization may however imply constraints in the way spaces can be used, which in turn may

bring about the need of experimentation with light approaches to temporary installations that can be rapidly modified and moved elsewhere.

At **La Friche**, every infrastructure (theatres, concert venues, exhibition venues, etc) has been conceived in a **reversible, adaptable and mutualised** way to foster collaborative working styles and keep freedom in future uses.

The **Blue House** initiative in **Dortmund** is an example of how the legal aspects of land use come into play in temporary activities. The ground floor in this historical building had formerly been a bar and it was zoned accordingly. Because “meanwhile use” does not have a recognised zoning category, the space remained under the existing zoning during the Blue House project. This limited the options for innovative temporary uses

The lack of a specific legal framework for meanwhile uses certainly poses specific challenges in meanwhile activation strategies. These include, for example, the **risk of uses that fit within a grey zone and that can be therefore illegal**. However, the lack of regulatory frameworks does not prevent meanwhile uses from emerging, especially when there is a lively social and cultural fabric.

Red Town in **Shanghai** is relatively small and ‘unorganised’, with a vibrant and quickly changing landscape of bars, artistic studios and other activities. The unique thing about this place is that it is downtown and has a green area where one can

go anytime. Because of that, a lot of informal uses happened because of an “unregulated area” which is quite rare for the city.

In 2012, the City of Barcelona initiated the programme **Pla Buits (Empty Spaces)** in order to support the temporary use of vacant spaces owned by the municipality that were left undeveloped after the financial crisis. The programme activated these spaces with financially self-sufficient, environmental, socially oriented activities initiated and managed by public or non-profit local entities. Some of these initiatives, such as **ConnectHort** played an important role of active citizenship and public consultation during the redevelopment of Poblenou and 22@.

Learnings

When temporary uses are not specifically regulated, the **active support from local authorities** such as Municipalities may be key to finding the proper regime.

Grey regulatory zones also require a certain degree of **creativity and experimentation** with light approaches to temporary installations and artefacts that can be rapidly modified and moved elsewhere.

Understanding **liability, security and licensing** regimes for different types of temporary uses may take a long time and require specific expertise. It is an important aspect to be considered as early as possible and budgeted accordingly.

Meanwhile Orchestrator

Financing temporary uses in urban regeneration

Meanwhile activation strategies can hardly take shape without financial support, which can be significant. Especially when applied intentionally and from the beginning of redevelopments, there is a general understanding of meanwhile uses as an **investment rather than a cost**, as they play a fundamental role in improving quality of spaces and increasing value, as well as in attracting prospective tenants. According to the way they are understood and strategized, they might be budgeted under different headings, such as communication and marketing, urban upgrading, or consultation and public engagement.

In **King’s Cross**, Argent maintained large investments in the arts and activation strategy throughout the whole regeneration process. Around 14 million has been spent over the course of the project (more than two decades), contributing much more than originally intended.

Meanwhile uses in **Dortmund** were one of the 29 activities envisaged in the redevelopment plan and budgeted as urban upgrading activities. They were carried out from 2009 to 2018 investing 242,000 euros from the primary urban redevelopment fund, 551,000 euros from additional public funds, and

32,000 euros from private investment, amounting to a total of **825,000 euros**.

Moreover, the **flow of funding can change over time** according to the regeneration strategy; funding can be higher at the beginning to sustain wide activation and attraction, and decrease over time hand in hand with the start of sales or leases. In other cases, it may instead increase, especially when meanwhile uses start to catalyse external funding as the effect of positive loops of collaboration set in place. Furthermore, **commercial meanwhile uses and subsidised rents and utilities** have been applied in many ACs, particularly the ones that have addressed themes such as upskilling & reskilling, job creation and micro enterprising. Clearly, these cases show that the waiting time in urban regeneration is not necessarily an unproductive period, as it can generate revenues and income for different groups.

At **Manifattura Tabacchi**, the three-year meanwhile strategy has seen a **gradual decrease** in the budget allocated. This followed the precise strategy of the developer to implement a marketing action, activating the space, attracting external resources and focusing progressively on 'commercial' priorities.

The **Dortmund Job Centre** was instrumental in providing the support and partnership needed to achieve a sustainable funding strategy for the **Blue House** and **Café U-Jack** initiatives in the beginning, including via direct funding and subsidization of utility bills.

The redevelopment of **Shanghai Sculpture Park (Red Town)** has been funded by one of the largest

banks in China. Arts and culture in the country are non-taxed, and there is a deep entanglement between real estate, cultural and creative sectors and finance. This may also explain the rapid rise in museums and cultural facilities in Shanghai in the past few years, for example within shopping malls.

Lastly, meanwhile uses developed through partnerships are also key for pooling financial assets, with the possibility to pool different funding schemes and investments that can also create **better conditions for legacy and more sustainable regeneration outcomes**.

In 2011, the social enterprise InWest eG was founded as a **district cooperative** with the aim of accompanying and supporting the positive development process initiated in Dortmund's Union Quarter. To this end, existing resources and competencies were pooled and new offers and services developed for the district. In cooperation with urban renewal, economic development, and cultural institutions, InWest eG oversaw the **"Creative industry incubator" (UNION QUARTER. KREATIV)**, one of the activities that were part of Rheinische Strasse's masterplan. Until 2018, the business activities of InWest eG were concentrated in the three business areas of real estate and location development, district-related services and project funding. Among the founding members of the district cooperative are the Planungsgruppe Stadtbüro, the Union Gewerbehof cooperative, the EWEDO GmbH. In addition, today's Union Quarter association and Neue Kolonie West e.V. were also involved in the foundation.

Learnings

Mixed meanwhile uses.

Combining different types of meanwhile uses - social, cultural, commercial, etc. - can help sustain the involvement of different audiences and publics, while creating better conditions for attracting and leveraging new sources of funding and support over time.

**Meanwhile Orchestrator,
Meanwhile Practitioner,
Developer, Public authority**

Mixed funding schemes.

Meanwhile uses may be hardly self-sustainable from a financial point view; however, they hold the potential to attract different interests, therefore making the case for mixed schemes of funding that include, for example, donations and sponsorships, grants, direct revenues from commercial uses, subsidized rents and utilities, corporate social responsibility. In this respect, a multi-stakeholder engagement strategy is also key to unlock a mixité of funding sources.

**Meanwhile Orchestrator,
Meanwhile Practitioner**

Funding for the long-term.

Meanwhile uses often unlock multiple forms of value that risk vanishing when they are over. Developers should have the ambition to sustain continuous activation and collaborative placemaking also after the redevelopment is complete, and to think about long term partnerships for this goal.

Meanwhile Orchestrator

Relational Highlights

In this section of the Portfolio, we capture insights related to the way meanwhile uses have been applied to unlock “software” upgrades and rewiring, including in terms of relational and social capital, engagement and collaboration, capacity building.

Relational capital and social trust

The creation of social capital and trust is a recurring goal of the various temporary initiatives considered for this Portfolio. Practices have been many, generally characterised by **temporary uses aimed at harvesting feelings, perceptions and desires, and through this establishing more direct contacts and social ties as key preconditions for trust**. Often, this is a preliminary step towards more sophisticated forms of temporary uses, as they help set the basis for community building, engagement and collaborative placemaking.

The **revitalisation of EC1 and New Centre in Lodz** has been largely **intra-community and bottom-up**. There were a series of events to present the space and its future functions, and several consultations and arts-led workshops and co-design events aimed at involving citizens in the creative expression of concerns and desires for the area, as a way to foster sense of belonging and pride.

At **Manifattura Tabacchi**, the developer took the decision of locating inside the area as the first temporary tenant, as a way to mitigate the risk to develop the regeneration project in a completely disconnected way from the feelings and expectations of citizens. Following the evolution of the construction site side by side with the city meant **living, working and observing daily interactions with the site**, so as to **establish direct dialogue with local communities** and better

capture and trigger desires and wishes for the **final uses**.

Furthermore, the vast majority of the ACs are characterised by meanwhile uses that address a multiplicity of publics. **Young people, artists, makers, designers** are most often at play, standing as driving forces of vitality and creativity that in turn may help boost changes in perceptions and feelings. **Families and children** are also important groups, especially when temporary uses work as ways to test or improve the final uses towards more liveability and life-work balance. **Disadvantaged, vulnerable and minority groups** emerge particularly in the context of meanwhile strategies driven by the public sector, although also present in private led ones. Generally, there seems to be less attention on **senior citizens or women** as specific beneficiaries of temporary uses, although many of them have addressed gender gaps and issues of loneliness and isolation through dedicated events as well as via temporary artefacts purposely designed to foster interactions.

The **microscale revitalization of the backyards** in the **Lodz** case is an example of a collective transformation of neighbourhoods through active engagement of **children and young people**. By supporting their agency and legitimacy to have a say in the process, they became an active part of the redevelopment, experiencing a growing sense of pride and belonging. Participants were trained in urban planning activities and could count on the support of students from the MA in Urban Revitalization of the University of Lodz.

At Manifattura Tabacchi, **attention has always been maintained towards the population in the**

neighbourhood. Many initiatives are promoted through social media channels, but also through flyers distributed in the neighbourhood in order to reach out to people that are not used to social media. Thanks to the variety in communication channels, audiences are quite diverse, ranging from the youngest to the oldest generations and including families and people from across the neighbourhood and beyond it.

La Friche hosts nearly 450,000 people every year. By opening its gates to every kind of actor over time, it has seen **a diversification of activities and interactions - from the social field to culture - and an evolution in the type of opportunities created**. Thanks to proximity, mutualisation of facilities and a shared willingness to maintain experimentation continuously in place, stakeholders have been inspiring and learning from each other, in an overall process that has advanced the symbolic meaning of La Friche as a place of underground culture and artistic expression.

Learnings

It is important that investors and developers show up and establish a direct relation with citizens and local communities at stake.

When meanwhile uses build incrementally - especially tapping into multiple issues such as education, job creation, sustainable lifestyles, etc., they may have higher chances to trigger reinforcing loops of trust creation and social capital

*Developer,
Public authority, Beneficiary*

Capacity Building

The vast majority of meanwhile projects across the ACs have been devoted to **capacity building, upskilling and reskilling, and empowerment in civic participation**. This has often happened as a result of consultation moments, as well as through observation and learning via temporary activities. Capacity building is both meant in the **short term** - increasing actors' capacity to act and engage within the process of development - and in the **medium term** - increasing actors' capacity to benefit from opportunities arising from developments.

King's Cross Construction Skills Centre derived from a Section 106 agreement, with the goal of creating **construction training and job opportunities** for people in the area, specifically but not exclusively for young people. It is most often a pathway into jobs in construction, such as carpentry, plumbing and bricklaying, but also into other areas of work as well. Whilst the centre has temporarily occupied different sites, **the vision has always been long term**: the skills centre is kept agile, maintaining the possibility of moving from place to place to ensure that the learning generated at King's Cross can be scaled to other sites in the borough and beyond.

Manifattura Tabacchi has created multiple capacity building activities over time for different publics, usually free of charge. For example, **digital laboratories** for children took place in the first year

of meanwhile activation. In addition, a rich variety of workshops, short trainings and lectures have been organised - around topics such as Do-It-Yourself production, reuse and recycling practices, urban greening, carpentry, pottery - often by involving temporary tenants (artists, makers and designers) as trainers.

In **Dortmund**, the meanwhile uses initiated by Ewedo (**BlueHouse, Café U-Jack, ProjectGarden**) were all focused on building capacity for long-term unemployed people as well as newcomers. The core idea of the initiatives in Dortmund's Union Quarter is to promote encounters between residents and visitors with and without a migration background. Participants experience regular daily employment, resulting in a strong motivation and in better professional development. Furthermore, in the garden project children are a key target group, and are provided with the opportunity to experience nature in urban space. Several training activities have been implemented around wood and technology, gardening, sewing as well as cooking and preparation of products from cultivation. To support these activities, the job centre set up a total of 6 job-sharing positions.

Communities of practice and Co-creation

Across the ACs, the various temporary initiatives often unfold through multi-stakeholder collaboration. These collaborations usually embrace

the full arc **from highly institutionalized and structured collaborations, passing through flexible and rapidly changing schemes, up to collaborations that run through serendipity**. There are no 'fixed' models, but rather multiple forms of collaboration that can take place across the various meanwhile uses developed. This is also **linked to the way the latter are orchestrated**, and to the collaboration culture that is channelled and sustained within the relational ecosystem of meanwhile uses. Generally, temporary uses have unlocked collaborations alongside a wide range of actors, including public authorities, businesses, non-profit organisations, cultural institutions, universities and informal groups of citizens. Moreover, the more meanwhile uses go beyond one off events and get stabilised over time (through activities that insist more regularly on a given space), the more we can observe an increase in the types and depth of synergies activated. **Co-creation and co-production** are diffused practices, which can happen, for example, via **co-design and co-management of the initiatives**, by **hosting events and activities promoted by external actors**, or through **open calls to action, including via prizes and awards**. Most often, collaboration through temporary activities is also a way to engage with prospective permanent tenants and allow them to nurture the site fabric already during the waiting time of urban regeneration.

Manifattura Tabacchi is currently experimenting with a platform approach where MIM, the company running meanwhile activation, seeks to position itself as the community host, while activities and contents largely come from the initiative of temporary tenants and external organisations. The

meanwhile activation has followed an incremental approach, with the recent **Superblast** initiative conceived as a call to action for all the creative energies of the city; more than **700 applications** were made in less than one month.

The **Collision Project** is Industry City's public art programme. It is conceived as an open source scheme where anyone can submit a public artwork idea through the website. Industry City funds the creation and pays the artist(s). The project allows for a diverse range of projects and contributors, also ensuring that support and visibility are granted to artists based locally in Sunset Park.

Skate Park Utopia in **Dortmund** is a meanwhile use that has been able to trigger bottom-up participation, becoming a source of inspiration for the Municipality. Differently from the Blue House, U-jack Cafè and the Project Garden, which were initiated by a consulting agency, the Skate Park was promoted by Skateboard Initiative Dortmund, an association that focuses on youth engagement. The constructions built in the lot were the result of the members' initiative and their collaboration with one another. The engagement of all players in the management, operation, and use has been one of the main elements of success. This involvement was achieved thanks to the dedication of the initiators and the channels of communication established with the city of Dortmund. The fact of being a very participation-friendly space brought about a **greater sense of responsibility in the initiators and users**, and a hands-on experience on how to creatively establish channels where effective collaboration can take place between initiators and local authorities.

As part of community-building strategies, temporary uses are also a way to create multiple communities of practices around different themes. **Citizen science, tech, arts & culture, skateboarding, digital manufacturing, urban greening, sustainable food production** are examples of themes that have been characterising many temporary uses across the ACs, with the emergence of communities of interest and practice that have also made use of digital platforms as a way to prolong collaboration occurring in physical spaces.

The **Media Lab** at La Friche has become a community hub for creative experimentation with tech and arts, involving a diversity of publics such as young people, artists, creatives and digital savvy makers. The Lab is particularly aimed at inclusion and empowerment of vulnerable and marginalised groups, following the idea of the digital environment as a commons. The Lab has proved to be highly successful, receiving over time more and more support also from local public authorities.

Ten years ago, when the use of skateboarding in the public realm was becoming more difficult in Marseille, La Friche created a **site for skateboarding**. The space is today a must for skate lovers from all over the world who love to travel and discover new skating spots.

ConnectHort in Poblenou was initiated in the context of the Pla Buits programme of the City of Barcelona for the temporary use of vacant spaces owned by the municipality. This initiative addressed social inclusion and empowerment by creating a **community of practice in permaculture**. The

project was initiated by two architecture and landscape collectives (ESPAsatge and Re-Cooperar) and the local neighbours association.

Learnings

Informality is an important ingredient for creative expression and innovation. If meanwhile uses are too structured and institutionalised, they may become less and less attractive and therefore lose traction.

Triggering **spontaneous citizen engagement** throughout meanwhile activation is key to fostering agency and legitimacy. However, this may turn out to be more difficult where there is strict and top-down control over meanwhile activation.

Meanwhile Orchestrator

The way meanwhile uses come to an end matters. If there are no real plans for this aspect, communities may feel less and less motivated in maintaining the improvements achieved.

Sudden interruptions of meanwhile uses may also disrupt the networks created. A smooth transition to permanence may heavily depend on the extent to which meanwhile uses are able to pool assets and resources, therefore keeping on activating both hardware and software aspects.

**Meanwhile Orchestrator,
Meanwhile practitioner,
Developer,
Local authority,
Beneficiary**

Temporary uses in urban regeneration

CO-BENEFITS, CRITICAL POINTS, SEEDS OF TRANSFORMATION

In this section of the Portfolio, we attempt to reconnect the different highlights through the lens of **co-benefits, critical points and seeds for transformation observed across the Advanced Cases.**

Importantly, not all the ACs have been monitoring and evaluating the various meanwhile initiatives implemented over time, and for many cases no impact evaluation has been made (or not yet) for the broader redevelopment. Therefore, the arguments captured in this section are partly based on measured evidence, and partly on perceptions and points of view mapped out during our research. Furthermore, they are complemented by the knowledge and practice capital that sits within the T-Factor project.

Co-benefits of meanwhile use in urban regeneration

As we could observe across the ACs, a key character of meanwhile uses lies in their potential to unlock different benefits for different publics, therefore accommodating an urban regeneration strategy that may have higher chances to be win-win.

In the following figure (p. 51), we provide an overview of core 'meanwhile use co-benefits' that we could observe across the ACs. Not all these benefits appear to be achieved in each case, and indeed their relevance and depth may differ from case to case. As we lack systematic evidence across all the various meanwhile initiatives analysed in our research, what we present in the figure is an 'in between' individual perceptions by the various actors and stakeholders reached out, specific monitoring and evaluation data available for some meanwhile interventions, and review of relevant documentation, including external research and media articles.

In the figure, we distinguish benefits as follows:

- **Direct co-benefits** refer to results achieved or perceived as such in a relatively short term. Typically, these co-benefits have a quantifiable and more tangible nature and often relate to the individual level.
- **Indirect co-benefits** refer to indirect benefits that often take shape and emerge in the medium term, and from the effect of reinforcing loops across direct co-benefits. In this case, co-benefits seem to revolve around value flows that are mostly qualitative and taking shape at collective level.
- **Spillover effects** refer to more long term and systemic co-benefits that in turn originate from mutually reinforcing loops across both direct and indirect co-benefits. Spillover effects may be the most unpredictable ones, as they largely depend on the degree and depth of achievement across direct and indirect co-benefits, therefore being deeply entangled with the broader regeneration path.

It is worth reminding that the redevelopment timeframe varies significantly across the ACs. Some of the regeneration projects are still ongoing, and there is no impact data available for the whole redevelopment yet; therefore, especially when it comes to indirect co-benefits and spillover effects, these are mostly based on the cases that are nearly or fully completed.

Direct co-benefits

Location

Meanwhile uses help establish location - a key driver of investment and attraction, creating in particular social and relational amenities that can in turn attract investment in physical assets and raise interest by prospective tenants.

Talent & Creativity

Meanwhile uses help attract young and creative talent which can be particularly relevant in areas suffering from ageing trends.

Dialogue

Meanwhile uses support dialogue with the actors at stake in regeneration processes, particularly the local communities. In doing so, they can be a lever for conflict mitigation.

Needs response and opportunities

Whether targeted at upskilling or reskilling, job creation, civic engagement, health and wellbeing, meanwhile uses address multiple needs and provide solutions already during the waiting time of urban regeneration.

Capacity-building

Meanwhile uses increase actors' capacity to both act and engage within the process of development and benefit from opportunities arising from it.

Collaborations & pooling of resources

Meanwhile uses are propellers of collaborations across multiple actors and sectors and help pool resources, including financial resources, knowledge and relational capital.

Indirect co-benefits

Attraction and property values

Meanwhile uses enhance the quality of spaces and therefore their value. This effect can go beyond the site under regeneration, and also unleash positive dynamics in surrounding areas.

Local commerce and services

As meanwhile uses attract new people in the area, they are an impulse for traditional businesses in renovating their offer, as well as in attracting new businesses, therefore making the area more lively and vibrant.

Perceptions

Meanwhile uses help revert negative perceptions relatively quickly. Arts and culture-led temporary uses combined with uses that explore aesthetics of spaces are also key to reduce anti-social behaviours, fostering a sense of pride, safety and security.

Social trust

As meanwhile uses unlock new relations and collaborations, they help establish social bonds and nurture trust, which is in turn a key precondition for relational, including inter-generational, capital.

City policies and strategies

When meanwhile uses engage with innovative themes linked to broader goals of sustainable urban development, they can become testbeds and showcases for city policies and strategies, for example related to slow mobility, zero waste, circular and sharing economy.

Spillover effects

Active, Inclusive and self-sustaining communities

Meanwhile uses can unleash more cohesive and inclusive communities that are actively engaged in the reactivation and care of sites in the long

run. They can help set the path toward collective empowerment, agency and legitimacy in the transition to more sustainable urban environments.

Thriving local economies

Meanwhile uses can boost the uptake of new civic economies rooted in sustainability and inclusion. They can trigger new products and services that redefine the way we experience cities - whether in terms of living, caring, learning, moving, supplying and enjoying - and thus serve as a push for more sustainable lifestyles.

New, shared urban assets

As meanwhile uses unlock new urban experiences, they can facilitate the emergence of new urban assets, as well as of new ways to invest and manage existing assets. These can be physical assets such as green areas, squares and streets, but also comprise digital commons, knowledge and collective intelligence.

Regenerative Spaces

Meanwhile uses can boost the transition to urban areas that are restorative and regenerative by design. Acting at the crossroad between resilience and adaptation, collective experimentation and capacity-building, meanwhile uses can help make the case for climate action in cities as a driver of preventative health, wellbeing, new jobs and quality of life within the boundaries of our planet.

Key Critical Points across the Advanced Cases

Strategic Risk

Urban regeneration is typically the field of multiple and interconnected risks that, most often, have a strategic nature. Financial exposure, capital deployment, investors' interests and reputation, relational capital, accountability - there are several factors at play that, especially in private-led regenerations, put risk at the core of the well-known trade-off between attraction of investments and attention to social impact. Especially when capital deployment is not patient, meanwhile activation strategies may be a source of specific risks; some meanwhile interventions addressed in our research clearly point to the conflict of interests that can emerge when temporary uses are successful, and they do not run hand in hand with real estate priorities. Yet, we have also observed that inaction and passive management of the waiting time is widely perceived as a driver of **much higher risks compared to an active, temporary use-driven approach to urban regeneration**. However, bringing meanwhile uses toward a true ground of

collective experimentation requires a **collective shift in mindsets**: for investors and developers, it requires incentives, mechanisms of rewarding and legitimacy vis-à-vis the pioneering and hardly predictable nature of temporary uses; for meanwhile practitioners and citizens at large, it requires empowerment and capacity to act throughout dynamics that can be conflictual, and that also demand shared risks and responsibilities uptake.

Inclusion

The focus of meanwhile uses on social inclusion is a recurring character across most of the ACs. However, there is often little evidence gathered on 'how much' and for 'whom' inclusion has been achieved, and some meanwhile initiatives addressed in this research are also surrounded by critics regarding this aspect. Arts and culture-led strategies of meanwhile activation also historically bring about the risk of niche and elitist urban spaces that might in turn pave the way for gentrification dynamics. Furthermore, when meanwhile uses explicitly address vulnerabilities, there might be a threshold above which certain types of target groups can be out of acceptance; developing temporary uses to address problems such as homophobia, homelessness or other extreme forms of deprivation often stand as a taboo in the conversation with both private and public players. Quite often, meanwhile uses report on the social groups they have involved, and there may be less attention around the who has not and why. This is a critical aspect that appears as crucial in mitigating the risk of displacement and segregation. If we can look at partnerships in

temporary uses also as a way to unlock structured cooperation with the third sector and social services, we may also begin to create the conditions for fully inclusive urban regeneration.

Legacy and value creation

The paradox of meanwhile uses is that the greater collaboration and value flows are, the higher is the risk of frustration and fights to make them stable. Several meanwhile uses across the ACs have generated conflicts and tensions with the arrival of permanent functions. This is what may also prevent developers from considering temporary strategies in redevelopments or limit the latter to one off events. Almost all the ACs have highlighted a fundamental point around the legacy of meanwhile uses, although from different perspectives and with different facets. Clearly, meanwhile uses can generate multiple flows of values - financial, social, cultural, relational - and for different publics. But when temporary activities end up, these flows may face a high risk of interruption and volatility, vanishing efforts. More than that, there might be the risk that financial and economic value remains in place and for a few actors, bringing about a major question mark around the way we can redistribute a value that is collectively generated. Therefore, the transition from temporary to permanent does not only need to be properly designed and managed; more than that, it requires reflection upon and exploration of possible models of co-governance and co-investment that can better allow positive outcomes to remain in place, grow and thrive.

Measuring the additionality of meanwhile uses in urban regeneration

Multiple and interconnected factors are at play when attempting to capture and measure the multiple added values of meanwhile uses in urban regeneration. The way meanwhile uses emerge; who steers and drives them; according to what ambitions and objectives; with what investment and resources; for how long they run; how they are governed and who they involve: these are just a few examples of factors that may determine the results and outcomes achieved by meanwhile activation. Moreover, these factors do not stand in isolation; rather, they are gears within the complex and multi-faceted system of urban regeneration where multiple interests usually converge and collide: the way these factors interact with each other largely sets the path of the regeneration journey, and gives shape to the benefits - and risks - that get unlocked along the way. Evaluation and impact assessment measures should go beyond single intervention measurement; rather, they should consider and explore 'attribution aspects' with a systemic lens of meanwhile orchestration - i.e. inquiring whether and how the whole meanwhile activation strategy stands as a mechanism for reinforcing loops of co-benefits and spillover effects in urban regeneration. Participatory processes that include all the voices at stake are a key precondition for holistic impact measurement, and the different stakeholders need to be clearly identified with their intentions at the outset. Moreover, it is essential to know if outcomes are positive or negative, their perceived level of

importance, if they are intended or unintended, meet the needs of the stakeholders, exceed a nationally or internationally recognized threshold.

Key Seeds from the Advanced Cases

In this Portfolio, and in the broader T-Factor project, we essentially look at the transformative potential of meanwhile uses in urban regeneration. We understand this transformation not only in terms of capacity of temporary uses to unlock a multitude of benefits at individual, collective and societal level; more than that, we inquire into temporary uses in their potential to transform initial plans and push the trajectories of urban regeneration towards higher ambitions of quality, inclusive and thriving spaces. It is a meanwhile activation designed and orchestrated by emergence at stake here, and the extent to which it can work *in between* the need of reliable paths, clear results and achievements on the one hand, and the demand for new and yet unexplored possibilities on the other hand. If this may stand as a new frontier in urban regeneration, what are the seeds across the ACs that can help

infrastructure transformative meanwhile practices?

We address this question through the lens of the infrastructuring framework presented above and its strategic, operational and relational dimensions. Three key questions guide the identification and capture of key seeds, each identified from the perspective and core motivations of the core actors at play in meanwhile uses and regeneration processes:

'What would enhance the value of the masterplan?' that we frame as a strategic question mainly driven by developers and investors.

'What would allow us to better capture emerging opportunities and uncover the most in terms of shared interests?' that we frame as an operational question mainly driven by meanwhile use orchestrators, intermediaries and practitioners.

'What would ignite long term success in meanwhile activation strategies?' that we frame as a relational question driven by citizens at large.

The figure below captures the core seeds across these three questions and puts the spotlight on the key seeds that may offer particular inspiration and learning for infrastructuring meanwhile uses towards transformative urban regeneration.

MEANWHILE USES

SEEDS OF TRANSFORMATIONS

SPILLOVER EFFECTS

INDIRECT CO-BENEFITS

DIRECT CO-BENEFITS

DISTRIBUTED AGENCY & LEGITIMACY AND MIXED TEMPORARY USES
Mixed temporary uses have higher chances of inclusion. Collaborative is a powerful lever of agency and legitimacy
see Dortmund Union Quarter, 22@, La Friche

PLATFORM APPROACH
Platform forms of collaboration and governance can sustain wide co-creation
see Manifattura Tabacchi,

CO-GOVERNANCE
Forms of co-governance and co-investments in temporary uses can have higher chance of legacy
see Dortmund Union Quarter, La Friche

PERMANENT MEANWHILE USE
The approach to meanwhile as a structural condition allows to foster continuous experimentation with new uses and interactions
see La Friche

/RELATIONAL

COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICES
Temporary uses rooted in CoP can trigger capacity building and inter-generational cohesion
see EC1 and New Centre Lodz, Dortmund Union Quarter, 22@, La Friche, King's Cross

M&E
Measuring the additionality of temporary uses requires participatory and integrated frameworks that consider socio-cultural, economic and environmental aspects
see Dortmund Union Quarter, King's Cross

/OPERATIONAL

FLEXIBLE MASTERPLAN
Temporary uses allow to unlock the flexibility of the masterplan through iterative sprints of development
see King's Cross, Lodz, EC1/New Centre Manifattura Tabacchi.

NOMADIC APPROACH
A nomadic approach to meanwhile uses allows to unveil the potential of spaces in a progressive manner
see Manifattura Tabacchi, King's Cross and La Friche

/STRATEGIC

CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions

In the *waiting time* of urban regeneration, planners and developers basically have two choices of approach, each with different nuances of application. On the one hand, they may consider this period mainly as a matter of technical and bureaucratic aspects to be managed efficiently. This approach - which inherently assumes that pre-identified uses and functions will stand the time test - still largely characterises urban regeneration in Europe, and often combines rigid and deterministic masterplans with top-down delivery. Alternatively, they may see the waiting time as a testbed for the future of our cities, building better conditions not only for risk mitigation but ultimately for quality regeneration.

The Advance Cases addressed in this Portfolio have clearly moved within this second perimeter. Whether applied intentionally or emerged as a consequence of favorable conditions, meanwhile uses have represented a key ingredient in their approach to the waiting time, contributing to or heavily determining the expansive and positive direction of regeneration paths and outcomes achieved. Meanwhile activation has been orchestrated in many ways, from case to case via a combination of different strategic approaches, operational and relational levers. As we have seen,

there is no unique model or path, but rather a multiplicity of options that depend on the existing planning culture, developers' experience, interests at stake, existing or emerging opportunities and challenges.

Despite their diversity, all cases show that meanwhile practices can trigger co-benefits. They can help build location, creating better conditions for higher quality spaces. They can accommodate more effective forms of public engagement, supporting direct dialogue between the different actors at stake and hence more opportunities for creating trust and social capital. They can address existing and emerging needs, and mitigate disruptions stemming from construction periods. Furthermore, meanwhile uses can catalyse creative talent and innovative entrepreneurship, hence contrasting isolation and cultural and economic deprivation. By unlocking new partnerships and alliances, they can enable wide collaboration and support pooling of resources around shared objectives. Above all, meanwhile uses hold the potential to change perceptions and feelings relatively quickly, therefore speaking directly to the DNA of decisions around where to live, work, spend free time, educate children or get healthcare - when these decisions can still be made.

Yet, meanwhile uses also cast shadows and bring about specific risks. As they raise expectations, they also raise risks of frustration and mistrust. They increase participation and engagement, and thus the risk that those who are not engaged are further pushed to the margins. They create attachment, and thus possible fights once temporary uses are over. They revert negative perceptions and feelings, yet with the risk of creating similar urban experience

everywhere, with no memory or true identity. Overall, meanwhile uses often trigger multiple flows of value that - once they are over - are at risk of volatilisation and capture by the few, often within an entanglement dynamic with gentrification processes.

In this context, not only is there an issue around the way we strategise, design and orchestrate meanwhile activation to reduce the risks mentioned above. Almost all the ACs - especially the ones where meanwhile uses have unlocked multiple co-benefits - pose a **fundamental question around the legacy of temporary uses, and the way we allow benefits to remain in place, grow and contribute to city scale and long term regeneration**. In turn, legacy brings about questions around **impact measurement, governance, capital and policymaking**. Not only do we need integrated and systemic frameworks that can better capture such co-benefits - oftentimes qualitative, long term and hardly monetizable. We also need to craft **policies, governance and capital deployment mechanisms premised on different ways of infrastructuring urban regeneration, built on new mechanisms of agency and legitimacy, new forms of investments, redistribution of value and long term visions**.

All the ACs may hold seeds and ingredients towards this new regeneration infrastructure. Friche's cooperative form and its 'permanent meanwhile'; the wide public realm strategy activated in King's Cross; the integrated and multi-stakeholder partnerships in Dortmund U and EC1 in Lodz; the platform approach of Manifattura Tabacchi; the activism observed in Poblenou and its capacity to change plans; IC's capacity to entangle meanwhile activation within the innovation economy and thus

An aerial photograph of a person sitting on a blue path that winds through a stylized landscape. The landscape is composed of large, wavy areas of red and pink, separated by white lines. There are two blue geometric shapes, one resembling a crystal or a stylized building, and another one partially visible on the left. The person is wearing dark clothing and is looking down at the path.

to unlock job opportunities at scale; further, the adoption of flexible approaches across all cases: these are valuable signs that meanwhile activation can drive alignment between public and private interests, and take on the mediation between quality spaces, returns on investment and shared risks. More than that, they all demonstrate that the waiting time in urban regeneration can be a **time of experimentation**, and temporary uses the labs where experiments can happen.

If we can begin to look at urban regeneration as a process of **infrastructuring the conditions - strategic, operational, relational - for collective agency, discovery and learning** on the one hand, and apply temporary uses with **higher ambitions of experimentation** on the other hand - embracing not only the software, but also the hardware aspects of **regulation, policy making, governance, funding**, we may contribute to set the path for a new architecture of urban regeneration. **One that thinks more strategically about the future and legacy we want to leave in the hands of the next generations.**

ANNEX

TEMPORARY USE CASES

DORTMUND U AND UNION QUARTER

> BLUE HOUSE

Period: 2009-2011

Funding: Public (Municipality) as part of the regeneration budget

Temporary Uses: Cultural, Social and Leisure

Target Groups: Young people; Unemployed people; residents in the district

Themes addressed:

Upskilling & Reskilling
Employment; Socialisation
Social Trust

Core objectives: Create better leisure opportunities for the residents of the neighbourhood; Provide qualification opportunities for long-term unemployed residents to improve their chance of finding a job

The **Blue House** resulted from a partnership between EWEDO and the landlord of the building, who was eager to host meanwhile uses in the vacant property to make it more attractive. The aim of the Blue House project was to create a meeting place in the Union Quarter through a better leisure offer but also as a strategy to provide qualification opportunities for long-term unemployed residents and combat radical-right presence in the neighbourhood.

The Blue House hosted two main types of activities: cultural and leisure events, and a qualification-for-employment program. Unlike other meanwhile uses in the UQ, the Blue House did not transcend into a permanent use. However, the Blue House project created a legacy of valuable learning experiences for other meanwhile uses to emerge in the area.

> CAFÉ U-JACK

Period: 2012 - ongoing

Funding: Public-private

Temporary Uses: Commercial, Leisure and Social

Target Groups: Residents in the Union Quarter and visitors; Unemployed People; Young people

Themes addressed:

Socialisation and social trust
Healthy and affordable eating
Employment

Core objectives: To create a meeting and socialisation place in the quarter that also creates job opportunities for long-term unemployed people and other vulnerable groups

Café U-Jack is located at Rheinische Straße 194 in a building that was used as a restaurant before but was vacant for several years. The look of the barricaded façade was not pleasant and rather typical for vacancies in this problematic, post-industrial area. With the U-Jack project the restaurant facilities were built back starting in 2012. Today, it contains kitchen facilities and is fully usable. The guest room is large enough to host events and meetings for and with residents of the Union Quarter. With the urban renewal of the city of Dortmund and the Dortmund job center, EWEDO GmbH has staged the U-Jack neighbourhood cafe as a social project with a cultural offer. Since the beginning of the project the café “U-Jack” has firmly established itself as a meeting place in the neighbourhood with low-threshold offers of balanced meals and small events for residents and visitors.

Furthermore, with the temporary use of the empty pizzeria the space was made attractive again for subsequent tenants. Today the cafe is open regularly from Monday to Friday. For U-Jack, it is important to have a varied range of food and drinks and also to offer dishes that the individual would usually not prepare at home. The neighbourhood café U-Jack has become a permanent institution in the Union Quarter. The actors in the neighbourhood know the meeting place, and there are cooperation and working relationships with many of them. There are regular reports about the U-Jack in the district publication Union Quarter-magazine.

The U-Jack Facebook page has been further developed and is updated weekly with the daily dishes. The stylised U - Jack logo appears on all publications such as handouts, menus and flyers and has created a high recognition value. The neighbourhood café is still to be understood as a low-threshold meeting place for the residents and visitors of the Union Quarter. It is an attractive and visible use of a formerly vacant property that upgrades the district and enhances its image in the long term.

> PROJECTGARDEN

Period: 2017 - ongoing

Funding: Public

Temporary Uses: Social and Cultural

Target Groups: Children and young people; families; residents; People with migration background

Themes addressed:

Urban greening

Safety

Employment

Social and cultural inclusion

Core objectives: To create a green space in an urban area as a driver of social relationships, nature-humans relation rediscovery and capacity building for different audiences and publics

The **Projectgarden** is located at Rheinische Straße 244. As part of the urban development in the Union Quarter, the Projectgarden aimed at enabling people to meet nature in an urbanized area. It is home to vegetables, wild plants and local herbs. The core idea of the project is to promote encounters and togetherness between residents and visitors with and without a migration background in the Union Quarter.

One focus of the Projectgarden is the work with children with and without a migration background from the district, who are provided with the opportunity to experience nature in urban spaces, also via training courses in areas such as wood and technology, gardening, sowing as well as cooking and preparation of the products from the cultivation. A nature adventure trail for children was also created. To support these activities as well as the maintenance and protection of the fenced area, the job centre has set up a total of 6 job-sharing positions. The long-term unemployed are given the opportunity to become involved in the project.

> SKATE PARK UTOPIA

Period: 2018-2020

Funding: Mix of public and private funding (self-sustained by the promoters)

Temporary Uses: Sport, Leisure, Social, Cultural

Target Groups: Children and young people

Themes addressed:

Sport and Leisure
Youth inclusion

Core objectives: To create an open, accessible and safe area for young people to convene together and practice skateboarding

The inception of **Utopia Skate Park** dates back to the collaboration between Skateboard Initiative and The Urbanists from 2015 to 2017. This collaboration consisted of building semi-mobile skating ramps that were placed in the U's forecourt during summers until it was forced to stop in 2018. No longer being able to skate at the front forecourt of the U, skateboarders began skating on the stairs located at the back of the U, which faced the empty lot that would become the skate park. A synergy between the city government and the Skateboard Initiative was created when a city official approached them with the offer of using the empty lot.

The skate park was launched in May 2018, initially lent by the city for 3 months. The agreement was further adapted and extended for 2 years, until its termination in 2020. The operations and development of the skate park were in large part financed by the Skateboard Initiative itself, which, as a well-established association, had the economic means to finance it and to get additional funding through the city, and enjoyed the support of its members and external donors. The main activity of the skate park was to provide an open space with skating structures that users could enjoy. The inception, development, and operation of the park is described as highly participatory and horizontal. Constructions built in the lot were often the result of members' initiative and their collaboration with one another. Aside from the skating structures, Skateboard Initiative built a bar hut, a stage, and overseas shipping containers as areas for safe storage.

The skate park was described as a place where one could go and where students and members of the creative industry often met. Thanks to the stage they had built, the park sometimes hosted concerts and similar cultural events. The park also hosted bigger events; one of them being an event organized by the Skateboard Initiative every year. They hosted a promotional event for JunkYard, a music initiative in Dortmund dedicated to organizing concerts and involved in the activities of a skateboard championship which had its main location in Düsseldorf. However, the most noticeable event was the Art of Skate exhibition, which was done in collaboration with UZWEI at Dortmunder U, members from the Bilbao skateboarding community and Azkuna Zentroa - Alhóndiga Bilbao

EC1 AND NEW CENTRE OF LODZ

> LIGHTHOUSE KEEPERS AND AREA HOSTS

Period: 2017-ongoing

Funding: Public

Temporary Uses: Social

Target Groups: Residents in the area with key focus on vulnerable residents

Themes addressed:
Social support and assistance

Core objectives: To reduce stress caused by temporary relocations, alleviate difficulties, and reduce tensions between temporarily displaced residents and the municipality

The problem addressed by this initiative is the difficulty experienced by the inhabitants of those urban degraded neighbourhoods that have been included in revitalisation projects. The implementation of the revitalisation changes requires the relocation of entire families, which often include elderly people or families with children.

The programme has been created to mitigate this stressful situation. It includes services of individual diagnosis, personalised advice and orientation in order to define specific support plans. Continuous monitoring and evaluation have also been applied, especially to determine whether more support was needed.

The programme has been developed with eight area **Hosts (AH)**, **eight Lighthouse Keepers (LK)** and **one Housing Specialist (HS)** that have worked in a complementary way, setting in place an integrated support service that has also seen multi-stakeholder collaboration across public and private players.

> BACKYARDS MICRO-SCALE REVITALISATION

Period: 2018-ongoing

Funding: Public

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural, Educational

Target Groups: Children, Young People

Themes addressed:

Civic Engagement

Youth inclusion

Urban Design & Planning

Core objectives: To improve the living environment and image of the area, create a sense of pride and ownership among residents, particularly children and young people

The initiative regenerated **tenement houses backyards** through participatory co-creation and implementation. The main goal of the programme was to empower children and young people from a low-income neighbourhood by actively involving them into the transformation of their living environment. The project was organised in an eight-step process where participants were engaged in urban planning activities.

This included assessment and diagnosis studies, involving local actors into the project, architectural designs, planning activities for the space, and several presentations of their assessments and projects and negotiations with neighbours and the municipality. Projects ended with the teams promoting their neighbourhood’s strengths to gain recognition and fight negative perceptions and feelings. Children and youth worked with the support of practitioners. Participants in the project also count with the support of the Lighthouse Keepers and students from the MA in Urban Revitalization.

Physical elements that were put into the space through these events, like the barbeque, remained in the backyards and will be there until these are renovated through the urban regeneration process. Thanks to this process, the idea of creating a ‘floating community centre’ emerged but the project was put on hold due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

> KNOCKING-OFF TIME IN ŁÓDŹ – FAJRANTY PO ŁÓDZKU

Period: 2014-2015

Funding: Public-private

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural

Target Groups: Families, Young People

Themes addressed:

Civic engagement

Core objectives: To inform people and communities addressed by the regeneration plan and engage them in a shared discussion aimed at mitigating possible tensions and conflicts

The initiative was a pilot project aimed at **improving the participatory and information strategy** for the city centre regeneration process and informing the Municipal Revitalisation Programme. The intention of the programme, which was funded by the City of Lodz through a grant for the Pilot Revitalisation Project from the EU's Technical Assistance Operational Programme and the Ministry of Infrastructure and Development, was to mitigate tensions and fears that arose among communities affected by the city centre regeneration process. People felt uninformed and forced to leave their homes without support.

Standard consultations and information spots that proved not to be attractive for residents were supplemented with numerous activities that established a dialogue between the residents and city representatives. The project combined public participation activities with cultural events aimed at making local culture more visible. The public participation events were facilitated by Urban Forms, a local NGO that was hired for the project. Participants were informed of the upcoming plans and they could share their concerns about the neighbourhood and the revitalisation process.

The consultation also included a media dissemination campaign with a dedicated newspaper that was distributed among residents and a radio programme addressed to the elderly. The findings, recommendations and lessons learnt from the consultations were collected in a Needs and Expectations Assessment and an open-access report that was collaboratively produced by Urban Forms, residents, and various local organisations, including schools. These were used to inform the Municipal Revitalisation Programme to prioritise revitalisation projects.

> ART-DRIVEN LEARNING WITH PIOTR JARGUSZ

Period: 2020

Funding: Public

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural, Educational

Target Groups: Families, Young People, Residents in the area, citizens at large

Themes addressed:

Arts & Culture

Citizen Empowerment

Core objectives: To use art as a driver to catalyse change in the neighbourhood, empower young people and women, and reduce negative perceptions and feelings

This initiative was an arts-based project aimed at reducing the negative stigma of a low-income residential area by bringing in a renowned artist that created a sense of pride in the neighbourhood. The project included art workshops for residents and passers-by at a public park that were facilitated by Piotr Jargusz and an outdoors pop-up exhibition.

The initial plan for the project was to first have the workshops and culminate the project with an outdoors public exhibition where Piotr Jargusz's and the participants' works would be anonymised and exposed together. This way only the artists would be able to recognise their work, busting the pride of the neighbours from a stigmatised neighbourhood. Due to the covid19 pandemic the initial project timeline was adjusted.

The initiative started with an outdoor exhibition of artist **Piotr Jargusz's** “Łódź - the city of women” series on advertising columns across the neighbourhood. The artworks became a temporary element of the streetscape of the neighbourhood, showing on the advertising columns with other posters until someone covered them. A week after the artworks were posted on the street advertising columns, a series of art workshops started in which residents and passers-by created similar large-format posters that were exposed at the park. The workshops were facilitated by Piotr Jargusz and supported by animators that encouraged people in the park to join. The initiative was very successful in attracting children and youth from the neighbourhood.

> MA STUDY PROGRAMME IN URBAN REGENERATION

Period: 2017-2020

Temporary Uses: Educational

Target Groups: Young Students

Themes addressed:

Urban Design and Planning
Capacity Building
Public-Private collaboration

Core objectives: To create knowledge and skills around socio-technical issues in urban regeneration processes that result in more citizen-friendly and bottom-up initiatives

The project emerged to address the tensions and dysfunctional cooperation between technical and social teams that worked in the **NCL urban regeneration project**. The aim of the programme was to create professionals that could work with a holistic approach to urban regeneration, breaking away with traditional silo-working approaches.

The urban revitalisation master combines technical and humanistic knowledge from six scientific disciplines (architecture, construction, sociology, educational sciences, geography, spatial planning, economics, and management). The programme saw a change of mentality among their students who were surprised by the complexity of urban regeneration projects. Students and academics with a technical background became aware of the importance of the social dimension and adopted more friendly positions with vulnerable groups.

Similarly, those with social backgrounds learnt to appreciate the importance of technical projects, logistics, infrastructure, communication or ‘green’ investments. Thanks to an agreement with the Municipality, students engaged in the regeneration process and the micro-revitalisation of backyards.

> EVENTS AT EC1

Period: 2007 - ongoing

Funding: Public-private

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural, Leisure

Target Groups: Families, Children, Young People,
Residents in the area and citizens at large

Themes addressed:

Arts & Culture

Science and technology

Core objectives: To make people rediscover the EC1 building, inform them about its regeneration plans and create an attractive image

The building of the former **EC1** power station became a stage for a series of cultural and touristic events that started in the year 2007 and will last when the building acquires its final function. These events were a response to social and media requests to understand what the plans for this space were after the electric power plant shut down in the year 2000 and the remained vacant. The overall strategy for the EC1 was not to close the space during the years of construction works but to allow residents and visitors in.

Construction works were strategically phased to allow for different parts of the building to be used at different times. Since 2007 the EC1 has hosted open days that has around 200 visitors and gave the building the title of “building of the year”, Museum Nights, exhibitions, Photo Days that attracted international audiences, and many other events. Through these events, people had the opportunity to see this iconic building that had always been closed to the public.

The events are organised by NGOs and external institutions and are often related to broader cultural events and festivals in Łódź with a well-established reputation. The local government owned the building and was the entity in charge of granting permission for the events, which was done free of charge. Through these events, EC1 gained recognition and changed the negative perception of a part of the city that used to have a bad reputation and that was very neglected

> “STITCHING UP THE CITY” PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOP

Period: 2011

Funding: Public

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural

Target Groups: Residents in the area and citizens at large;
Urban Planning professionals and experts

Themes addressed:
Civic engagement

Core objectives: To build a sense of joint responsibility among citizens, professionals and city officials on city-making processes and have urban plans that are more inclusive and responsive to the citizens needs

The aim of the workshops was to develop an **urban policy and spatial development concept for the NCL** to better integrate it with the historical city centre. They were funded and organised by the City of Lodz as a response to the interest from urban planners and architects in the projected changes in the NCL area. The Polish Urban Planners' Association (TUP) was introduced into the project as a neutral actor that could mitigate political tensions.

They facilitated the process and that brought know-how into the process. The workshops were attended by urban experts from different technical and social disciplines, residents, local businesses, city officials, and representatives from different local institutions and associations. Participation from local actors, however, was limited because the hermetic language used by experts and insufficient publicising of the events. The workshops were organised in three stages: A first informative session, an urban concepts and guidelines design workshop, and a closing event to summarise the workshop and select the winning projects. Financial prizes and a prize of Lodz citizens were awarded, and all proposals can be seen in the City of Lodz website.

The discussions of the workshops and the proposed concept design and guidelines contributed to the revision of the masterplan, particularly the area around EC1 and its connection with the historical city centre. Nevertheless, not all the proposals from the workshop have been implemented. This caused some disappointment among some of the participants. Overall, however, the workshops succeeded in catalysing important mindset changes among decision makers around concepts like connectivity, pedestrian spaces, citizen participation. It also created a legacy of events that have given Lodz a good reputation for participatory planning.

MANIFATTURA TABACCHI FLORENCE

> SUMMER 2018

Period: June-September 2018

Funding: Developer's Funding with minor co-funding from the Municipality

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural, Leisure

Target Groups: Families; Children; Senior Citizens; Young People; Citizens at large

Themes addressed:

Industrial Heritage
Urban Greening
Tech
Arts & Culture

Core objectives:

- To raise attention and interest of citizens and communities around the site;
- To communicate its forthcoming transformation as a new contemporary pole in the city

Summer 2018 refers to the rich programme of events and laboratories developed at the reopening of the site in 2018. Through this first round of temporary activities, the new property aimed to promote the re-discovery of Manifattura, opening the doors to the city, getting closer to the citizens and engaging in a dialogue with the local communities. Temporary activities included:

- The **Open Day**, in which Manifattura officially reopened to the city. Throughout the day, members of MTDM provided the visitors with information about the regeneration project and its planned evolution. Visitors could hear recordings of stories connected to the site, and enjoyed music, theatre and dance performances, which in turn involved more than 50 local artists. During the Open day, the art residencies - planned to be installed in the following months - were also activated; activities for children such as woodcraft labs were also organized;
- **Round tables with citizens** discussing and sharing perceptions and feelings related to the regeneration project;
- **Festival Au Desert**, a multicultural music project already existing in Florence, that has been brought in Manifattura for this special occasion. Created as a network for contemporary creation between Africa and Europe, it celebrates cultural diversity through music and sociability. In addition to concerts by the protagonists of Mediterranean music and Tuareg and Berber culture, the festival delivered DJ sets, meetings, screenings and readings on the topic of migrations;
- **Sparx Camp**, digital laboratories targeting children and young people;
- **Florence Folks Festival**, an urban popular festival combining tradition and contemporaneity, local and international dimensions, through music, food and conviviality;
- **God is green**, a two weekends festival dedicated to green practices. During the festival, artistic performances, social dinners, blind food tastings, green design market, DJ sets, contemporary circus, street food, bicycle rides, workshops for children and workshops to design new community models have been organized.

> B9

Period: 2019 - Ongoing

Funding: Developer's Funding

Temporary Uses: Cultural, Artistic, Making facilities, Commercial, Leisure

Target Groups: Makers; Designers; Artists in different disciplines

Themes addressed:

Arts & Culture
 Making
 Conviviality and Co-working

Core objectives:

- Attract artists, artisans, bistro, café, restaurants, shops, willing to open their activity inside the spaces of MT;
- Create a recognised public space dedicated to making and culture in Florence;
- Prototype a new form of co-working for creatives and craftspeople.

Temporary uses implemented in B9 include:

- **Maker space:** a space with **4 ateliers and 4 laboratories** set up ad hoc for the makers; a multifunctional event space/club; cafeteria; a bistro; a craft beer tasting area; an outdoor courtyard equipped with a stage for shows; a green area with biodynamic vegetable garden and a children's garden. The ambition of Manifattura is to create a space dedicated to **contemporary artisans** - the makers - in various fields: **art, millinery, tailoring, ceramics, restoration, but also conviviality and cuisine.**
- **Toast Project Space:** an independent art gallery that was set up in the exporter's lodge at Manifattura. As a place of reflection on contemporary styles and practices, it hosts works from emerging artists, opening up wider discussions between the public and the artists. Toast is the brainchild of Stefano Giuri, an artist who was part of the first cycle of Artistic Residencies at Manifattura, the three-year project curated by Sergio Risaliti which has been relaunched with its second edition in September 2019;
- **Temporary Installations, the Spirit of Experimentation and Innovation:** The presence of artists and their creative and research activities have allowed the history of the site to be rediscovered and to reanimate abandoned areas, instilling a new and deeper meaning to the regeneration work that is being undertaken in the area. It was **not clear from the beginning** to the property that contemporary art would have been the prevalent focus of the meanwhile experimentation: it has been **the result of a discovery process** that started the first year with the art residencies experimentation and deepened more and more in the following years, given the increasing attraction that these kinds of initiatives achieved. To expand the spaces dedicated to art, experimentation and creativity, the first floor of B9 has been completely dedicated to **temporary installations and exhibitions from contemporary artists.** The contemporary art initiatives involved both emergent and renowned artists and exponents of the cultural, fashion and design world at local and international level.
- **Fabbrica dell'Aria** (Air Factory), curated by neurobiologist Stefano Mancuso and PNAT, is the first prototype of an innovative solution which reduces indoor pollution, specifically created for Manifattura. This device uses and enhances the capacity of plants to absorb and degrade atmospheric pollutants.

> NAM NOT A MUSEUM

Period: 2019 - Ongoing

Funding: Developer's Funding

Temporary Uses: Cultural, Artistic, Making facilities

Target Groups: Artists, students, citizens at large

Themes addressed:

Arts & Culture

Young artists residencies

Art experimentation

Core objectives:

- Experimenting a permanent use of some spaces in Manifattura Tabacchi to generate impulses for the programmatic profiling of its location, establishing a new activity profile that is carried on in a new form even after it ends.
- Promote an initiative within the Florence contemporary art scene dedicated to artistic residencies and experiences.

The meanwhile initiative “**NAM – Not a Museum**” refers to an interdisciplinary program taking place between March 2020 and the end of 2021. NAM explores the relationship between arts, nature and science, thanks to artistic residencies, exhibitions, performances, meetings and the involvement of the community.

The program is articulated into exhibitions, festivals, performances, and artist residencies developed alongside Florentine institutions such as Museo Novecento and Palazzo Strozzi. NAM was developed in order to experiment with a further “piece” of the final Factory, with the aim of placing it permanently within the regenerated complex. Public art, performance, video, cinema, art publishing, radio and dissemination activities are part of the ecosystem that Not A Museum aims to become, capable of reaching all types of public.

The provocative term of “Not a Museum” counteracts the traditional experience of museums and art spaces, offering a flexible space for artists that encourages the exploration of different types of collaborations and new forms of art.

FRICHE LA BELLE DE MAI

> SKATEPARK

Period: 2008 - ongoing

Funding: Self - financed

Temporary Uses: Sport, Leisure, Social, Cultural

Target Groups: Young people, citizens at large

Themes addressed:

Urban sports and Culture

Core objectives:

- Create space where youngsters of Marseille can meet and learn skateboarding as a means of transport in the city, exploring new points of view
- Prevent delinquency, facilitate inclusion and inter-generational relationships

The **skatepark** is coordinated by the public aim cooperative managing La Friche (legally: SCIC), while the land belongs to the city of Marseille and run by SCIC Friche la Belle de Mai.

Board Spirit Marseille has an agreement for mostly using the skatepark but any operator resident can use the space as they wish (for concert, performances, rehearsal etc.). The site used to be an abandoned space of the factory. Since 1990 it's been used alternatively as rave party space, event spaces but also parking lots and technical storage spaces. Ten years ago, when the use of skateboarding in the public space was becoming more and more difficult in Marseilles, La Friche offered Marseille's residents a site dedicated to this practice. Today the site is a must for skate lovers from all over the world, who love to travel and discover new spots.

Designed by Constructo, an agency specialising in skatepark architecture and engineering, it is based on pre-existing urban architectural forms, offering modules suitable for street skateboarding.

> MEDIALAB

Period: 1993 - ongoing

Funding: Mainly public, with self-financing component

Temporary Uses: Cultural, Social

Target Groups: Media practitioners, Young people, citizens at large

Themes addressed:
Art, media and creativity

Core objectives:

- Create space where media practitioners and citizens of Marseille can have access to resources, workshops and creative practices related to digital arts and cultures
- Promote digital culture, facilitate inclusion and inter-generational relationships

The **Medialab** is the heir of the Cybercafé created in 1993 and of the “Espace Multimedia” which has been one of the firsts of this kind in France; a space of resources, workshops and creative practices related to digital arts and cultures, free and open to all. It aims to influence artistic and cultural practices by providing the capacity to experiment and by fostering networking and peer to peer learning, both among the practitioners of La Friche and people from the neighborhood.

Situated in a closed space of 50m², the Media lab is equipped with computers, tools for Virtual and Augmented reality as well as books and magazines. The space, coordinated by La Friche cooperative (SCIC) and managed mostly by one of the resident organisations (Zinc), is specially set up for facilitating meetings and workshops. The Medialab relies on national local fundings and EU fundings to the resident operator. It is co-financed by the SCIC by valorising human resources and technical skills.

Publics have always been involved in la Friche development through workshops, co-creation of the space and access to its equipment. The Medialab holds activities such as workshops of digital practices to allow children to develop their creative sense by discovering artworks, as well as a “Repair Café” promoting the do it yourself culture with workshops on the repairing of computers or household appliances.

> EMPTY SPACES

Period: 1991 - ongoing

Funding: Depending on case to case

Temporary Uses: Cultural, Social

Target Groups: Residents, artists, institutions

Themes addressed:

Temporary uses

Core objectives:

- Design future uses of the place
- Include a varied plethora of actors in the decisions on meanwhile uses of La Friche

Since 1991 different spaces in La Friche have been kept as 'empty spaces' to allow activities **"to be tested"** on a permanent basis. Some of the initial empty spaces have been transformed throughout the years and have now a new use. However, a blank space to imagine new uses and functions is always left intentionally in La Friche.

Throughout the years, a majority of collaborative events since la Friche creation were addressed to explore possibilities of use of each vacant space of the ex-factory. Some of these spaces have been transformed throughout the years, with an action coordinated by the Société Coopérative d'Intérêt Collectif (SCIC) which incorporated La Friche in 2007. This governance solution has been central to manage and shape meanwhile spaces with no predefined destination, allowing the development of experimentations by bringing sufficient coordination effort without reducing the freedom of innovation of single actors. Means and technical aspects (security, public hosting, etc.) are shared and co-defined within the SCIC, with responsibility shared between producers.

Although the system to make decisions on the use of spaces seems to be well organised and structured, the decisions still depend on the artistic willingness of their promoters, giving a large range of freedom to invent new uses and events in still vacant spaces in the site. Since La Friche's creation, many collaborative events were run to explore possibilities of use of each vacant space of the ex-factory. Some spaces are still empty and used as an experimentation ground for activities shaping the future of the place.

KING'S CROSS

> SKIP GARDEN

Period: 2009-2019

Funding: Mix of private and public funding

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural, Educational

Target Groups: Families; Children; Young People; Communities on site; Citizens at large

Themes addressed:

Civic engagement
Urban Greening
Healthy Eating
Capacity Building

Core objectives:

- To support people of all ages in reconnecting with urban nature
- To empower children and young people in education around ecology, and to build social and relational capital
- To contribute to more cohesive and resilient communities

The **skip garden** was a garden made up of a series of skips and other semi-mobile structures, so that it could be relocated hand in hand with the progress of the development. It was managed by an educational and environmental charity and as such, became the site for many educational and outreach activities throughout the years.

It was started in 2009 by Global Generation who work to create healthy, integrated and environmentally responsible communities, focussing in particular on children and young people. The guiding pillars of GG's work are both working with people of all ages in order to support a connection to the natural world, but importantly also providing opportunities for children and young people to make a difference. GG are positioned to give children and young people a voice, and this has been foregrounded through their Mayor of London backed Generators program, which has been running since 2018, working with young people on social action projects.

Many of the initiatives that happened in the Skip Garden were ideas by young people. The construction companies were involved as co-creators with Global Generation at each of the Skip Garden locations. They helped develop the whole programme of learning and volunteering days, and GG would also carry out reflective practice with them about building relationships in the community, communication and sustainability. This practice also became embedded into practical doing days at the garden.

> KING'S CROSS CONSTRUCTION SKILLS CENTRE

Period: 2008 - ongoing

Funding: Public-Private

Temporary Uses: Educational and Training

Target Groups: Young People; Unemployed people

Themes addressed:

Upskilling & Reskilling
Job creation and inclusion

Core objectives:

To improve construction training and job opportunities for people who live in the area, specifically but not exclusively focussing on young people

The creation of the **King's Cross Construction Skills Centre (KXCSC)** is a product of the planning agreement, known as Section 106, between the developer, Argent, and the local planning authority, Camden Council. The S106 agreement at King's Cross is attached to the planning permission and there are various duties that the developer, Argent, are obliged to agree to and carry out across the phasing of the development.

The residential areas surrounding the King's Cross development site have suffered long term deprivation in terms of education, employment, health and other factors. Therefore, it was seen to be crucial that the construction of the project at King's Cross could directly benefit local residents in terms of education and employment. Therefore, it was identified early on that the construction of the King's Cross development had the potential to provide training and jobs for local people.

> RELAY ARTS PROGRAMME

Period: 2008-

Funding: Mostly developer-funded

Temporary Uses: Artistic, Cultural, Educational, Leisure

Target Groups: Artists, Creatives, Citizens at large and communities on site

Themes addressed:
Artistic production

Core objectives:
To foster a change in negative perceptions and feelings around the area and support attraction and interest

Argent put together a public bid for the role of curator on the King's Cross site around 2010. This was overseen and advised by the Arts Council, who had been involved on the site running an Arts Council England residency programme in which two artists were in residence on the King's Cross site, Ellie Reid in 2008/9 and Graham Hudson in 2009/10.

The curation of the public arts programme was intended to change every couple of years, hence the name 'Relay'. The intention by Argent was to use the arts programming as a way to draw people through the site. Starting with the initial installation, IFO, at the South of the site, outside the entrance to King's Cross and St. Pancras stations, drawing people up through the avenues leading to the Granary Building, which was the location for Felici Varini and Richard Wentworth's pieces, and finally towards the back of the site at the Lewis Cubbit Park where the King's Cross Pond Club was located.

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> HANGAR IN CAN RICART

Period: 1997 - Ongoing

Funding: Private foundation managing the space relies on mixed funding

Temporary Uses: Industrial building

Target Groups: Young people, practitioners in cultural production

Themes addressed:

Arts, Culture and Creativity
Civic engagement

Core objectives:

To build a space that meets the needs of young people, a kind of house for youth associations, where young people can promote debates, events, creativity and artistic production

Hangar is an arts and research production factory set up in the late nineties in one of the buildings of Can Ricart, an abandoned industrial complex that the City of Barcelona bought off from the Marquis of Santa Isabel. The complex is on a regular route for metal scrapers. Hangar started off as one of the few arts productions and research centres in Catalunya.

It is managed by a foundation that operates under a Board that is re-configured every three years to guide the direction of the centre. While Hangar may have initially been conceived as a temporary use for a vacant space, we cannot say it is a temporary use anymore since it is not going anywhere. The building next to Hangar is now used to house a Youth Centre where many youth-led associations of Poblenou, young people, artists and cultural operators have an opportunity to get to know each other and work together.

The funding comes from the City. The Youth centre promotes several pop-up events such as a flea market. Hangar has been in the area for over 20 years. It has helped the dynamization of the area and the impact has been a movement towards the formalisation of the meanwhile uses with the apparition of some pop-up uses.

> SUPERILLES (SUPERBLOCKS)

Period: 2016 - Ongoing

Funding: Public

Temporary Uses: Streets

Target Groups: Residents; Families

Themes addressed:

Mobility & Pedestrianisation
Urban greening

Core objectives:

To test temporary public space and pedestrianisation solutions to transform the model of the city towards a more pedestrian friendly, clean and inclusive city that stimulates socialisation and proximity economy

The “**superilles**” are sections of the city constituted by several urban blocks where the streets are pedestrianised with tactical urbanism methods. They are planned and implemented by the planning department of the City of Barcelona. The “superilla” in Poblenou was the pioneer one and it includes nine blocks distributed in a 3 by 3 grid. Today there are five superilles in Barcelona and there is a project to create green pedestrian axes that expand the concept across a large portion of the city.

The superilla was first implemented only with temporary traffic calming elements such as mobile street furniture, trees planted on pots, and bollards, street paint, and management tools like changing the direction of streets. Over the years, the space has been tested with different measures and solutions and it has slowly become a consolidated space with permanent elements. The space is however in continuous evolution and more changes are expected to come. Among these there are the urban gardens proposed by a local collective. The superilla transformed a space that was car-dominated, both in terms of traffic and parking, into playgrounds, spaces for people to practice sports, sit and gather. The project has been the object of much contention. Different groups of local actors in support of and against the superilla have been created. Opponents mostly include nearby residents who saw traffic increase in their roads and business owners who lost clients.

They were particularly outraged by the way the project was implemented while residents were away on holidays and without being informed. They also include people who consider that the superilla contributes to the general gentrification process in the neighbourhood. On the other hand, supporters celebrate having safe spaces for children to play and for people in general to meet, for the reduced noise levels, and for the positive image and popularity that the superilla gave to the area.

> **CONNECTHORT AND PLA BUITS (EMPTY SPACES)**

Period: 2012 - Ongoing

Funding: Public

Temporary Uses: Social, Cultural, Artistic, Educational, Leisure

Target Groups: Civic Groups, residents, families

Themes addressed:

For Pla buits: Adaptive use of public space
Each specific project within Pla Buits has its own themes.
For ConnectHort: Urban greening, social, healthy eating, capacity building

Core objectives:

For Pla Buits: To regenerate the urban and social fabric while preventing unwanted activities (such as squatting)
For ConnectHort: To create a space for social gathering and the promotion of permaculture

The **ConnectHort** (ConnectGarden) emerged from the Pla Buits (Empty Spaces Plan), a programme from the City of Barcelona for the temporary use of vacant spaces owned by the municipality. This programme emerged in 2012 as a response to social demands for the utilisation of the numerous vacant plots in the city that were left undeveloped after the financial crisis.

The programme activates these spaces with financially self-sufficient, environmental, socially-oriented activities initiated and managed by public or non-profit local entities. The aim of the programme is three-fold: To promote active citizenry, to regenerate the social and urban fabric, and to prevent the emergence of other “non-desirable” uses by filling-in the space. Pla Buits operates through open calls for proposals open to local registered civil society organisations.

The activities are initially planned for a three-years period that can be extended overtime, but it does not allow for permanent construction. To date, there have been two open calls for proposals and a total of fourteen MUs have been implemented. ConnectHort is an urban garden that holds educational workshops in permaculture for neighbours and is open every Saturday for anyone to visit. The project was initiated by two architecture, urbanists and landscape collectives (ESPAsatge and Re-Cooperar) and the local neighbours association.

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